

**Intelligent Trust and Security Orchestration for 6G Distributed
Cloud Environments**

Deliverable 2.2

Initial Architecture of iTrust6G Platform

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List of Acronyms

3GPP	3rd Generation Partnership Project
5GC	5G Core
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ATT&CK	Adversarial Tactics, Techniques, and Common Knowledge
BPMN	Business Process Model and Notation
CACAO	Collaborative Automated Course of Action Operations
CIF	Collective Intelligence framework
CNCF	Cloud native Computing Foundation
CNF	Containerised Network Function
CRA	(EU) Cyber Resilience Act
CRITs	Collaborative research Into Threats
CTI	Cyber-threat Intelligence
DB	Database
DL	Deep learning
ENI	Experiential Networked Intelligence
ENISA	European Union Agency for Cybersecurity
ETSI	European Telecommunication Standardisation Institute
FIRST	Forum of Incident Response and Security Teams
FL	Federated Learning
GenAI	Generative AI
GUAC	Graph for Understanding Artifact Composition
HE	Horizon Europe
IBI	Intent-based Interfaces
IBN	Intent-based networking
IBS	Intent-based system
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
IdP	Identity Provider
IMA	Integrity Measurement Architecture
IP	Internet Protocol
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
IoC	Indicator of Compromise
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
JU	Joint Undertaking
JWT	JSON Web Token
LCM	Life-Cycle Management
MANO	MANagement and Orchestration
MISP	Malware Information Sharing platform
MITRE	The MITRE Corporation
ML	Machine Learning
NBI	Northbound Interface
NFV	Network function virtualisation

NFV-IFA	NFV Interfaces and Architecture
NIS2	Second Network and Information Security Directive
NIST	National Institute of Standards and Technology
NSD	Network Service Descriptor
O-RAN	Open Radio Area Network
OASIS	Organization for the Advancement of Structured Information Standards
PDP	Policy Decision Point
PEP	Policy Enforcement Point
PETs	Privacy-enhancing techniques
PNF	Physical Network Function
R&D	Research & Development
RA	Remote Attestation
RFC	Request for comment
RoT	Root of Trust
SBOM	Software Bill of Materials
SDO	Standards Development Organisation
SIEM	Security Information and Event Manager
SLSA	Supply-chain Levels for Software Artifacts
SMO	Service Management Orchestration
SNS	Smart Network & Services
STIX	Structured Threat Information Expression
TAXI	Trusted Automated Exchange of Indicator Information
TC	Technical Committee
TCG	Trusted Computing Group
TI	Threat Intelligence
TIP	Threat Intelligence Platform
TPM	Trusted Platform Module
TTPs	Tactics, Techniques, and Procedures
VNF	Virtualised Network Functions
WP	Work Package
YETI	Your Every Day Threat Intelligence
ZSM	Zero-touch Service Management
ZT	ZT
ZTA	ZT Architecture

Executive Summary

This deliverable, iTrust6G D2.2, reports on the first iteration of iTrust6G architectural activities led in work package 2 (WP2). It reports the work conducted in task 2.2 (T2.2) by detailing and justifying the initial version of the system architecture of iTrust6G, to serve as a baseline for all the technical work conducted in work WP3/4/5/6. A revised version of this architecture that accounts for lessons learnt will be reported in the upcoming iTrust6G D2.4.

The key technological areas relevant to iTrust6G are identified and improvements over state-of-the-art - where applicable- are proposed toward an end-to-end system security architecture capitalising on zero-trust (ZT) principles to enable a trustworthy 6G service management platform, addressing dynamic network and application-level security requirements, aligned with the technical objective of the project. Besides the specification of the general system architecture, iTrust6G D2.2 provides the following:

- Definition of the main processes for the continuous trust assessment between services, computing resources, and users;
- Definition of the main processes for risk and threat evaluation on platform resources and mitigation;
- Definition of the main processes for the cyber-threat intelligence generation and ingestion for trust assessment.

Chapter 1 provides an overview of the intents of the document, the targeted audience, and explicates how it is expected to contribute to the execution of work in other WPs of the project.

Chapter 2 positions the projects regarding the key enabling areas by presenting relevant state-of-the-art. Selected domains cover (i) intent-based security policy, (ii) collaborative threat intelligence, (iii) trust model and evaluation, and (iv) the security management. The state-of-the-art, ongoing R&D initiatives supported by Open-Source communities and European research program, and relevant standardisation communities susceptible to benefits from those topics are analysed and identified.

Chapter 3 explains the main iTrust6G doctrine to adapt ZT principles from traditional architecture to satisfy anticipated security and trust requirements for the next generation of mobile networks.

Chapter 4 introduces the preliminary system architecture of iTrust6G aligned with the doctrine from Chapter 3 and the requirements stated in iTrust6G D2.1 [1]. Essentially, different planes and actors expected to interact with iTrust6G platforms, and their separation of concerns are defined. The different functional components, and the information they exchange, are then methodologically specified.

Chapter 5 sets into motion the work described in Chapter 4 by detailing the main processes leveraging the functional architecture. Specifically, details of core processes related to trust assessment, cyber-risk and threats to handle, and cyber-threat intelligence generation and ingestion for trust assessment are provided. This includes the formalisation via sequence diagram involving the components of the platform.

Chapter 6 summarises and closes the document.

1 Introduction

The increased openness, technological heterogeneity and involvement of different stakeholders in mobile networks have complicated the establishment of a perimeter-based security management. This statement has motivated the research perspective on the adaptation of the zero-trust (ZT) paradigm for the next generation of mobile networks.

To that extent, **iTrust6G** aims at providing an end-to-end system security architecture that capitalise and adapt ZT principle to deliver a trustworthy 6G service management platform. This design accounts for dynamic network and applications-level security requirements.

In detail, **iTrust6G** proposes to iterate over the introduction and design of a programmable service platform covering the management of cloud, edge and data plane resources, interacting with third-party applications and having a governance emphasis on trust. More specifically,

- The architecture permits the design and implementation of a holistic trust model serving the continuous re-evaluation the stakeholders their components and their interaction,
- The architecture draws upon collaboration between several tenant stakeholders by exchanging cyber-threat intelligence affecting operated service as trust indicators, to facilitate the evaluation of trust from the local context,
- The architecture includes security orchestration to cover the full cycle of detecting and remediating security risks and threats, such as vulnerabilities that could potentially be exploited. This orchestration contributes to evaluating trust by assessing the overall security context and the system's exposure to potential threats.

The current document, **iTrust6G** D2.2 "*Initial architecture of iTrust6G platform*", describes and justifies the initial design of the architecture proposed by **iTrust6G** to serve as a baseline for the work conducted in technical WPs by framing the architecture of the system. This is a consolidation of the work conducted in the T2.2, "Architecture design", contributing to the following technical results of the projects:

- General system architecture for trust and security in a multi-tenant 6G telecom platform, covering the cloud continuum,
- Definition of the main processes for the continuous trust assessment between services, computing resources, and users,
- Definition of the main processes for risk and threat evaluation on platform resources and mitigation,
- Definition of the main processes for the cyber-threat intelligence generation and ingestion for trust assessment.

1.1 Structure of the deliverable

The document is structured as follows:

- Chapter 2 reviews the current state-of-the-art in pivotal domains for **iTrust6G's** concept. The state-of-the-art regards the work conveyed by scientific communities, industry and standardisation contributors.
- Chapter 3 discloses **iTrust6G's** vision to adapt ZT paradigm into building an end-to-end security management framework and serving as foundation for the architecture project.
- Chapter 4 describes the first version of the architecture, highlighting the main layers, components, actors, and explaining their individual roles.

- Chapter 5 explains how the different components conceptually interact to justify how the main processes are implemented.
- Chapter 6 concludes the document.

1.2 Relation to the work packages

The architecture described in this deliverable is built upon the requirements and the use-case definition defined in T2.1 and consolidated in iTrust6G D2.1. The different components definition and their interaction will serve as initial design material for the work conveyed in WP3, WP4 and WP5; and will impact the definition of the testbed, the platform integration strategy and the evaluation campaign to be conducted in WP6. Finally, the state-of-the-art analysis will foster dissemination activities and smooth the liaison activities with industrial communities and standardisation bodies.

1.3 Expected audience

The content of this document should firstly interest the technical partners of the project (researchers, architects and developers) who will implement and evaluate the features of the project while ensuring the eventual integrability of their work. The document should also interest the dissemination and exploitation team in the project by aiding the identification of destination communities susceptible to be interested in the project's results. Finally, as this deliverable is public, this document is also destined to an external audience of scientists and practitioners in service and network security willing to discover iTrust6G's vision on ZT applicability to the next generation of mobile networks, and the anticipated advancement in the state-of-the-art to be provided by the project activity.

2 Relevant State-of-the-Art

The iTrust6G concept plans to associate the advancements of four different fields to conceive a novel end-to-end system security architecture enacting ZT management in the next generation of mobile network:

- The intent-based security policy, applying the expression of intent of system constraints to define a policy applicable to security management, trust evaluation and threat intelligence supervision,
- The collaborative threat intelligence, questioning how different entities can collaborate around to gathering, exchange and consumption of cyberthreat specification applicable to trust evaluation and security management,
- The trust model and evaluation, considering methodologies to scrutinise entities participating in the network to continuously determine their risk to represent a threat to other assets,
- The security management, conducting protective actions on the network resources to maximise their security posture before and during cyber-threat occurrence.

This chapter provides a review for the state-of-the-art of the different fields to position the novelty of iTrust6G architecture.

2.1 Intent-based security policy

An intent is defined as a set of operational goals (that a network is supposed to achieve) and outcomes (that a network is supposed to deliver) specified in a declarative manner without specifying how to achieve or implement them [2]. Thus, intents apply several important concepts simultaneously [2].

- Provides data abstraction: users don't have to worry about low-level device configuration and nerdy controls.
- Provides a functional abstraction of specific management and control logic: users don't even have to worry about how to achieve a specific intent. A desired outcome is specified, and Intent-based systems (IBS) automatically determines the course of action on how to achieve that outcome.

2.1.1 Research initiatives

Intent-based security policy is an emerging approach in network security management that focuses on defining security policies based on high-level business intents rather than low-level technical specifications. This paradigm shift aims to simplify the complex task of managing security in dynamic and heterogeneous network environments by abstracting the underlying infrastructure and enabling automated policy enforcement. The following overview explores the current challenges in intent-based security policy and research advancements.

A concrete current challenge regarding Intents is to handle the coexistence between non-intent interfaces and intent-based interfaces in line with the ZSM architecture, as it is stated in the ETSI ZSM group [3].

Also, the security challenges inherited from SDN pose significant risks to the overall security of IBN. As with SDN, IBN has a centralized network controller. Centralizing the control plane makes it an attractive target for attackers. Another SDN inherited challenge is the vulnerability to denial-of-service (DoS) attacks and the presence of a single point of failure, which can result in the loss of service availability to the IBN controller [4].

AI is also present by enhancing network security in Intent-Based Networking (IBN), automating security configurations, ensuring consistency, and minimizing human errors. It enables real-time threat detection and response by analysing network traffic for anomalies, allowing for quicker incident management. AI's

predictive analysis capabilities help anticipate potential security breaches by identifying patterns, facilitating proactive measures. Centralized control through AI simplifies the management of security policies, reducing the risk of policy conflicts. Additionally, AI continuously adapts to new threats by learning from past incidents, ensuring that security measures are always up to date. These features collectively strengthen the security framework of IBN systems [4].

2.1.2 R&D initiatives

As a novel approach to manage security between different entities, the Intent-based is a topic which has been and is present in many projects and groups. For example:

- **FISHY Project** [<https://fishy-project.eu/>]: here was designed and implemented the human-centric FISHY user interface. Four internal components in the Intent-based interface were designed and implemented, using natural language processing techniques, powered by artificial intelligence and machine learning, and considering the different requirements and constraints.
- **HORSE Project** [<https://www.horse-6g.eu/>]: the Intent-based Interface is a pivotal module to in charge of enhancing the orchestration operations related to data quality and AI-based data analysis. The IBI sending the intents to other modules starting the workflow, in this case in terms of security mitigations.
- **5G-CLARITY Project** [<https://5gclarity.com/>]: in his project was developed an Intent-Based interface using natural language and includes two management entities as part of the Intelligence: Intent Engine and AI Engine.
- **HEXA-X-II Project** [<https://hexa-x-ii.eu/>]: here, the Intent-based framework translates the received intents into specific domain resource requests, evaluates their feasibility before provisioning, validates possible conflicts among new and existing intent deployments and constantly checks that the expectations in each intent are properly fulfilled.

2.1.3 Standardisation

Regarding standardization, there are some RFCs covering this topic. RFC (Request for Comments) are a series of formal documents from the IETF (Internet Engineering Task Force) outlining standards and protocols related to the Internet and networking technology.

- RFC 9315: “Intent-Based Networking - Concepts and Definitions”
[<https://www.ietf.org/rfc/rfc9315.pdf>]
- RFC 9316: “Intent Classification”
[<https://www.ietf.org/rfc/rfc9316.pdf>]

Also, in ETSI (European Telecommunications Standards Institute) which is an independent standardization organization responsible for developing global standards for telecommunications, broadcasting, and other electronic communications networks and services. Specifically in the working groups ENI (Experiential Networked Intelligence) and NFV-IFA (NFV Interfaces and Architecture):

- ETSI GR ENI 013 V1.1.1 (2023-01): Experiential Networked Intelligence (ENI); Intent Policy Model Gap Analysis
[https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_gr/ENI/001_099/013/01.01.01_60/gr_ENI013v010101p.pdf]
- ETSI GR ENI 015 V4.1.1 (2024-05): Experiential Networked Intelligence (ENI); Processing and Management of Intent Policy
[https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_gr/ENI/001_099/015/04.01.01_60/gr_ENI015v040101p.pdf]

- ETSI GR ENI 008 V2.1.1 (2021-03): Experiential Networked Intelligence (ENI); InTent Aware Network Autonomicity (ITANA)
[\[https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_gr/ENI/001_099/008/02.01.01_60/gr_ENI008v020101p.pdf\]](https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_gr/ENI/001_099/008/02.01.01_60/gr_ENI008v020101p.pdf)
- ETSI GS ENI 033 V4.1.1 (2024-08): Experiential Networked Intelligence (ENI); Definition, Requirements and Procedure of Intent Policy Multi-Stage Translating
[\[https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_gs/ENI/001_099/033/04.01.01_60/gs_ENI033v040101p.pdf\]](https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_gs/ENI/001_099/033/04.01.01_60/gs_ENI033v040101p.pdf)
- ETSI GS NFV-IFA 050 V4.5.1 (2023-10): Network Functions Virtualisation (NFV) Release 4; Management and Orchestration; Intent Management Service Interface and Information Model Specification
[\[https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_gs/NFV-IFA/001_099/050/04.05.01_60/gs_NFV-IFA050v040501p.pdf\]](https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_gs/NFV-IFA/001_099/050/04.05.01_60/gs_NFV-IFA050v040501p.pdf)

And in 3GPP (3rd Generation Partnership Project), a global collaboration between telecommunications organizations that develops protocols for mobile telecommunications, including 3G, 4G (LTE), and 5G technologies. Technical Specification and a Technical Report has been produced:

- 3GPP TS 28.312: Intent driven management service for mobile network
[\[https://portal.3gpp.org/desktopmodules/Specifications/SpecificationDetails.aspx?specificationId=3554\]](https://portal.3gpp.org/desktopmodules/Specifications/SpecificationDetails.aspx?specificationId=3554)
- 3GPP TR 28.912: Study on enhanced intent driven management services for mobile networks
[\[https://portal.3gpp.org/desktopmodules/Specifications/SpecificationDetails.aspx?specificationId=3969\]](https://portal.3gpp.org/desktopmodules/Specifications/SpecificationDetails.aspx?specificationId=3969)

2.2 Collaborative threat intelligence

In the ever-evolving cyber ecosystem, traditional approaches for cyber security that concentrate on identifying and addressing vulnerabilities, weaknesses, and configurations inwardly are vital but insufficient. To be effective, defence against current and potential threats requires an external focus on comprehending the capabilities, intentions, and behaviour of the adversary. To make informed defensive decisions, it is necessary to have a balanced understanding of both adversaries and organization's perimeter. The development of this understanding is known as cyber threat intelligence (CTI).

The generation of CTI involves the collection, analysis, and dissemination of information about potential or current threats to an organization's cybersecurity. The state-of-the-art in CTI generation leverages advanced technologies and methodologies to provide actionable insights and enhance the overall security posture. CTI itself poses a challenge because no single organization can collect enough information to create and maintain accurate situational awareness of the threat landscape. This limitation is overcome by sharing of relevant cyber threat information among trusted partners and communities. Through information sharing, each sharing partner can achieve a more complete understanding of the threats they face and how to defeat them. Collaboration in threat intelligence sharing brings together organizations from various industries, sectors, and regions. This diversity of perspectives and expertise enriches the collective knowledge pool and enables a more comprehensive understanding of the threat landscape.

2.2.1 Research initiatives

Research initiatives in CTI are diverse and involve multiple stakeholders, including government agencies, academic institutions, industry leaders, and non-profit organizations. These initiatives aim to advance the understanding of cyber threats, develop innovative technologies for threat detection and mitigation, and promote effective sharing and collaboration in the cybersecurity community. Current research focuses on fields like:

2.2.1.1 Federated Learning

In ML-based CTI applications it is necessary to share samples of both benign and malicious network data, which may lead to the leakage of information about the intended user, endpoint, or application. To get around these restrictions, federated learning is necessary to expand the learning models' knowledge base while protecting user privacy. FL is an advanced ML technique that overcomes the limitations of centralized learning. It enables model training across multiple decentralized sources, each keeping its local data private. This approach enhances privacy and security since data is not shared with others, while also reducing latency, power, and storage needs by minimizing data transmission. In [5] the suitability of FL-based collaborative CTI sharing for network intrusion detection is being explored and shows that there is a slight trade-off between FL's privacy enhancement and classification performance compared to a centralized approach.

2.2.1.2 Blockchain for CTI Sharing

The cybersecurity community is becoming increasingly interested in the convergence of CTI with blockchain technology, since it can completely transform the threat intelligence landscape due to some of its characteristics, namely auditability, transparency and consensus. CTI and blockchain work together in a way that can support cybersecurity initiatives and help solve the persistent issues of securely handling and disseminating critical threat information. This collaboration though requires careful attention on their combination due to blockchain negatively affecting the performance of these systems in terms of speed, scalability as well as security. The authors in [6] [7] surveys, showcase multiple works, that have investigated the implementation of blockchain in collaborative CTI scenarios.

2.2.1.3 Deception Technologies

There is considerable research being done on the technology that generates CTI and analyses attacks in a deceptive environment. ML and DL techniques are utilized to ascertain which attack vectors are used, even though it is certain that the source accessing the deceptive environment has adverse intents. A common term for these tools and platforms is "honeypot", which primary goal is to mimic a productive environment, that allows defenders to gather more data about tactics, techniques, and procedures (TTPs), in order to produce CTI [8], [9].

2.2.1.4 AI involvement in CTI

The use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) is becoming more prevalent in CTI to analyse and identify patterns in large datasets, improving the accuracy and speed of threat detection. AI offers a potential solution, automating and enhancing various tasks, from data ingestion to resilience verification [10]. The potential of AI to process and analyse vast amounts of data rapidly, makes it a good candidate for CTI processing. As a result, ML increases the efficacy of CTIs for threat detection by creating fast and effective algorithms that yield correct findings in threat analysis. Moreover, privacy concerns can be addressed with ML approaches for CTI sharing by utilizing privacy-enhancing methods including compressive privacy, differential privacy, and synthetic data generation [6] (e.g. [11], [12], [13]). Finally, the adoption of Generative AI (GenAI) in the field of CTI shows an incredible potential to the field of cybersecurity [14]. Detection, incident response, automated security patching and threat intelligence enhancement are among the areas that GenAI can assist [15], however, it is still in the early stages and the degree of effectiveness is yet to be confirmed.

2.2.2 R&D initiatives

The necessity to improve system security against sophisticated cyber threats is driving research and development in the field of CTI. As this field is advancing, new approaches are being investigated, and issues are being addressed through several research initiatives. The projects under the umbrella of the SNS that

focus on this field:

- **PRIVATEER** [privateer-project.eu]: With a privacy-by-design methodology, PRIVATEER's goal is to create novel security enablers for 6G networks. A privacy-friendly CTI sharing is part of the overall architecture of the project. Its objective is to guarantee the confidentiality and encryption of all interactions by using an API that leverages distributed shared search indexes. These indexes allow trusted entities to query indicators like IP addresses and systems with relevant data to verify sharing permissions and provide a list of entities holding the requested data for further transfer.
- **RIGOUROUS** [<https://rigorous.eu/>]: The goal of this project is to recognize and resolve the primary dangers to cybersecurity, trust, and privacy that endanger the network, devices, computing infrastructure, and services of the future. CTI sharing is being promoted by RIGOUROUS as an essential tool that aids in gathering and analysing relevant data regarding possible threats, vulnerabilities, and attacker strategies. To facilitate the safe exchange of CTI data a privacy-preserving solution is proposed, which is based on the combination of a standard TIP, such as MISP, and a policy-based anonymization module that can apply several prevalent PETFs.

To jointly defend against the sophisticated cyberattacks of today, apart from the initiatives in research projects, many businesses have demonstrated a growing willingness in the last several years to exchange data, information, and intelligence regarding emerging threats. As a result, some software solutions have been put into practice to better accommodate this issue that serve as platforms for exchanging cyber threat intelligence [16]. There are several open-source platforms, such as MISP [17], YETI [18], OpenTAXII [19], OpenCTI [20], CIF [21], CRITs [22] and more, that are compared based on their attributes, leading to their evaluation in terms of various criteria that include integration capabilities, automation and hardware requirements [23], [24].

2.2.3 Standardisation

Standards Development Organizations (SDOs) play a crucial role in facilitating collaborative threat intelligence by creating and promoting standards that enable secure, efficient, and structured sharing of threat information across different organizations and sectors. These efforts help to enhance the overall cybersecurity posture by providing a common framework and language for threat intelligence. The key SDO efforts in collaborative threat intelligence are highlighted here:

2.2.3.1 OASIS (Organization for the Advancement of Structured Information Standards)

The OASIS standardisation body contributes in two different directions toward collaborative threat intelligence, that can be considered by iTrust6G project:

1. The OASIS Cyber Threat Intelligence (CTI) Technical Committee (TC) was chartered to define a set of information representations and protocols to address the need to model, analyse, and share cyber threat intelligence. The CTI TC focuses on development and standardization of STIX (Structured Threat Information Expression) and TAXII (Trusted Automated Exchange of Indicator Information) under the OASIS open standards process. With STIX and TAXII OASIS is a) trying to provide a common framework for sharing threat intelligence, enabling interoperability between different systems and organizations, b) support for automated sharing and ingestion of threat intelligence, reducing the time and effort required for manual processes and c) provide a detailed representation of threat data, allowing for comprehensive analysis and action.
2. A CACAO (Collaborative Automated Course of Action Operations) playbook is a workflow that is similar to a business process model and notation (BPMN) playbook for security orchestration and

automation. It is expressed in JSON and comprises a series of actions to be taken based on a logical process. A CACAO playbook's execution can be time-dependent or initiated by an automated or manual event or observation. Additionally, cyberspace defence functions including threat hunting, detection, investigation, prevention, mitigation, remediation, and attack simulation can all be supported by it [25].

<https://www.oasis-open.org/>

2.2.3.2 FIRST (Forum of Incident Response and Security Teams)

FIRST is actively working on the standardization of incident response processes and activities, to improve the interoperability of incident response teams. First focuses on development of the CVSS (Common Vulnerability Scoring System) and IEP (Information Exchange Policy). With these two frameworks, FIRST tries to ensure that vulnerabilities are assessed using a common scoring system, facilitating better understanding and prioritization while in parallel to provide guidelines for secure and effective information sharing, enhancing collaboration and trust among different entities.

<https://www.first.org/>

2.2.3.3 ISO/IEC (International Organization for Standardization / International Electrotechnical Commission)

The IEC and the ISO collectively issued ISO 27010. In addition to instruction provided in the ISO 27000 family, the standard guides the incorporation of information security management across information sharing groups. ISO/IEC 27010 provides controls and instructions on adopting, implementing, maintaining information security in inter-organisational and inter-sector communications. Moreover, towards consistency and automation ISO/IEC 30111 provides guidelines for vulnerability handling processes. It outlines best practices for identifying, reporting, and addressing vulnerabilities.

[ISO/IEC 27010:2015](#), [ISO/IEC 27000 family](#), [ISO/IEC 30111:2019](#)

2.2.3.4 NIST (National Institute of Standards and Technology)

NIST develops cybersecurity standards, guidelines, best practices, and other resources to meet the needs of U.S. industry, federal agencies and the broader public. With SP 800-150 “Guide to Cyber Threat Information Sharing” [26] NIST provides guidelines for establishing and participating in cyber threat information sharing relationships. This guidance helps organizations establish information sharing goals, identify cyber threat information sources, scope information sharing activities, develop rules that control the publication and distribution of threat information, engage with existing sharing communities, and make effective use of threat information in support of the organization’s overall cybersecurity practices.

2.2.3.5 ENISA (European Union Agency for Cybersecurity)

ENISA contributes to EU cyber policy and enhances the trustworthiness of ICT products, services and processes with cybersecurity certification schemes. ENISA provides regular reports that provide an overview of the current cyber threat landscape, based on shared intelligence from various stakeholders. Additionally, ENISA focuses on the sharing of CTI in the EU by providing guidelines and best practices for sharing threat intelligence within the EU, aiming to enhance collaboration and improve the overall security posture [27].

<https://www.enisa.europa.eu/>

2.2.3.6 MITRE Corporation

MITRE provides the Adversarial Tactics, Techniques, and Common Knowledge (ATT&CK) framework that

catalogues TTPs used by threat actors. The MITRE ATT&CK framework provides a common language and structure for describing cyber threats and is widely used in threat intelligence sharing. ATT&CK is a curated knowledge base and model for cyber adversary behaviour, reflecting the various phases of an adversary's attack lifecycle and the platforms they are known to target. The tactics and techniques abstraction in the model provide a common taxonomy of individual adversary actions understood by both offensive and defensive sides of cybersecurity. It also provides an appropriate level of categorization for adversary action and specific ways of defending against it.

[\[https://attack.mitre.org/\]](https://attack.mitre.org/)

2.3 Trust model and evaluation

A trust model is a framework that defines how trust is established, managed, and assessed between entities within a system. These models are designed to ensure that interactions are reliable and secure, enabling actors to make informed decisions based on the trustworthiness of other entities.

Evaluation of trust models involves assessing their effectiveness in accurately predicting and measuring trust. This process includes analysing their robustness, scalability, and adaptability to different contexts and threats. Effective trust evaluation mechanisms ensure that trust is correctly assigned and maintained.

2.3.1 Research initiatives

Trust models are foundational in the realm of cybersecurity, providing frameworks to evaluate and ensure the trustworthiness of systems and their components. One crucial application of trust models is in Remote Attestation (RA), a process that allows a verifier to ensure the integrity of a remote system. Trust models for RA are designed to ensure that the prover behaves as expected [28], without malicious tampering. Traditional antivirus software relies on signature-based detection methods, which compare the code of potential threats against a database of known malware signatures. While effective against known threats, this approach struggles to detect new, previously unseen attacks, often referred to as zero-day attacks. Trust models and RA offer a promising solution for detecting such novel threats. This is achieved performing behavioural analysis and integrity checking, ensuring that only expected code has been executed on a system [28].

There are several key trust models in RA. Static attestation verifies a system's integrity at boot by comparing start-up values against known good ones to ensure a trusted state. Dynamic attestation, or run-time attestation, extends this by monitoring the system's behaviour during operation, providing real-time assurances. The Linux Integrity Measurement Architecture (IMA) is commonly used for dynamic attestation, recording file hashes upon access for real-time integrity verification.

The Root of Trust (RoT) establishes a trustworthy baseline essential for maintaining system record integrity. RoT, a key component in a computing system's security architecture, includes hardware, firmware, and/or software mechanisms that are implicitly trusted. The Trusted Platform Module (TPM) serves as the most common hardware RoT, supporting security features like secure boot, platform attestation, and system identity verification.

The field of trust models in RA is rapidly evolving due to increasingly complex systems and sophisticated threats. Research now aims to enhance the security, performance, scalability, usability, and flexibility of attestation mechanisms to address new challenges.

2.3.2 R&D initiatives

The field of trust models and RA is under active research and development, driven by the need to enhance system security against sophisticated cyber threats. Various research projects and working groups are

dedicated to advancing this field, exploring new methods, and addressing existing challenges. Here are reported main projects related:

- **Keylime** [29]: maintained by the Cloud Native Computing Foundation (CNCF) and it is a RA framework oriented to the cloud enabling the monitor of remote nodes.
- **Veraison** [30]: collaborative project focused on implementing IETF standards related to attestation. It provides various libraries designed to facilitate the creation of attestation services. The primary aim of Veraison is not to offer a ready-to-use application, but to provide essential functions that help standardize the formats of custom attestation frameworks. By doing so, Veraison supports the development of interoperable and consistent attestation mechanisms across different platforms and use cases.

In the area of supply chain security, several important R&D initiatives have been carried by the Linux Foundation, specifically, under the umbrella of the **Open-Source Security Foundation (OpenSSF)** [31], a global collaboration dedicated to improving the security of open-source software. It has spearheaded numerous initiatives to enhance the security of the software supply chain, such as:

- **GUAC** (Graph for Understanding Artifact Composition): it's a software supply chain observability tool. It ingests SBOM, Software Bill of Materials, and maps out relationships between software components. This visualization helps identify vulnerabilities and weaknesses, track dependencies, and understand the overall security posture of the software supply chain.
- **SLSA** (Supply-chain Levels for Software Artifacts): a security framework for defining and measuring the security of software supply chains. It establishes a set of requirements and practices to ensure the integrity, provenance, and traceability of software components.
- **Scorecard**: an automated tool that assesses open-source projects for security vulnerabilities. It assigns scores based on various security best practices and can be used in conjunction with SLSA and leveraged by GUAC.
- **Sigstore**: a digital signature infrastructure designed to provide provenance and integrity for software artifacts. It uses cryptographic techniques to verify the authenticity and integrity of software packages, preventing tampering and ensuring that they come from trusted sources.

2.3.3 Standardisation

Given the applicability of Remote Attestation (RA) across various contexts, numerous working groups have attempted to address the complex task of standardizing the process. While some groups have concentrated on specific fields like cloud computing or IoT, the most relevant efforts are highlighted here.

2.3.3.1 Trusted Computing Group (TCG)

TCG develops and promotes open standards for hardware-based security. Their work on TPMs provides a foundation for many RA mechanisms by ensuring secure storage and cryptographic operations. It focuses on TPM 2.0 specifications [32], attestation protocols, secure boot processes.

2.3.3.2 IETF RA Procedures (RATS) Working Group [33]

This working group is focused on defining interoperable protocols and architectures for RA. They established some guidelines for attestation architectures and proposed standardizations for attestation evidence and results.

2.3.3.3 National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST)

The NIST conducts research on cybersecurity standards and guidelines, including those related to RA [34]. At the level of the security of the supply chain, given that the topic has also some crucial impact on the legal aspects, several regulations are acting *de-facto* as standardisation bodies by dictating several technical and functional requirements to be implemented. Several referential assimilable to standards are listed below.

2.3.3.4 Network and Information Systems Directive 2 (NIS2):

The NIS2 regulation introduces several requirements related to supply chain security, that may vary depending on the nature of the organization and the sector in which it operates. The main requirements are:

- **Risk Assessment:** Organizations must identify and assess the risks posed by their supply chain and evaluate the security measures implemented by suppliers and their ability to mitigate risks.
- **Have incident response plans:** Organizations must have incident response plans in place to address security incidents that may originate from their supply chain.
- **Notify authorities:** Organizations must notify relevant authorities of any significant security incidents that affect their supply chain.
- **Maintain records:** Organizations must maintain records of their supply chain security activities, including risk assessments, due diligence, incident response plans, and communications.
- **Implement security measures:** Organizations must implement appropriate security measures to protect their supply chain, such as encryption, access controls, and vulnerability management and update security measures continuously.

2.3.3.5 European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA):

The European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA) has published several reports and guidelines related to supply chain security. These resources assist organizations in translating the NIS2 regulation's requirements into concrete technical and organizational measures that ensure compliance:

- **"Good Practices for Supply Chain Cybersecurity"** (June 13, 2023): covers how to identify and assess risks in the supply chain, supplier relationship of essential and important entities with service providers, vulnerability handling in products and components, and quality of products and cybersecurity practices of suppliers and service providers.
- **"Threat Landscape for Supply Chain Attacks"** (July 29, 2021): This report aims at mapping and studying the supply chain attacks that were discovered from January 2020 to early July 2021.
- These resources can be found on ENISA's website: <https://www.enisa.europa.eu/>

2.3.3.6 EU Cyber Resilience Act, 2023 (CRA)

While NIS2 focusses on the broader organization level, Cyber Resilience Act (CRA) focusses on the individual product level. CRA directly addresses the security of the software supply chain and introduces a set of requirements for manufacturers of products with digital elements, including software. These requirements aim to ensure that software developers and vendors implement security measures at every stage of the development process, from design and coding to testing and maintenance. This includes addressing potential vulnerabilities in third-party components used in the software supply chain.

The key provisions of the CRA related to software supply chain security include:

- **Risk assessment**, to identify and address potential vulnerabilities in their products, including

those introduced by third-party components.

- **Secure development practices:** Manufacturers must follow secure development practices, such as using secure coding techniques and conducting regular security testing.
- **Incident response:** Manufacturers must have plans in place to respond to and mitigate security incidents, including those involving third-party components.
- **Transparency:** Manufacturers must provide consumers with information about the security features of their products and any known vulnerabilities.

2.4 Security management

The evolution of 6G networks introduces a new set of complexities for security management. Unlike previous generations, 6G is expected to support massive-scale applications with real-time, distributed, and dynamic network architectures. These networks will rely on enhanced security frameworks that can handle high scalability, ultra-low latency, and cross-domain interactions, all while maintaining the security and privacy of user data. The iTrust6G project addresses these challenges by developing an integrated security framework that combines AI-driven techniques, ZT Architecture (ZTA), and the alignment of emerging security practices with global standards. The project's goal is to build a resilient, adaptive, and secure 6G environment capable of responding to both known and emerging threats in real-time.

2.4.1 Research initiatives

A key focus of iTrust6G is the use of AI-driven security for dynamic threat detection and network protection. AI and ML are critical in processing the vast amounts of data generated by 6G networks and detecting anomalies that may indicate a breach or malicious activity. AI models are trained on behavioural patterns of both users and devices, allowing for proactive identification of threats even before they manifest as clear security incidents [35]. This predictive capability is crucial in a 6G environment where the response time to threats must be instantaneous. However, the deployment of AI introduces new risks, particularly in the form of adversarial attacks, where attackers attempt to exploit vulnerabilities in AI models themselves [36]. To mitigate this, iTrust6G focuses on creating resilient AI systems that are robust against manipulation and can continue functioning effectively under attack.

Another key component of iTrust6G's security framework is ZTA, which departs from traditional perimeter-based security models. ZTA assumes that no entity, whether inside or outside the network, should be inherently trusted. Every device, user, and service must undergo continuous authentication and authorization processes [37]. This principle is particularly relevant for 6G, where decentralized and distributed environments are the norm. iTrust6G's ZTA implementation builds upon the NIST Zero Trust Architecture [37], with specific adaptations for 6G's large-scale, low-latency applications. The use of ZTA ensures that even if one part of the network is compromised, the rest of the system can continue operating securely. Moreover, iTrust6G integrates principles from ETSI ZSM (Zero-Touch Network and Service Management), specifically focusing on security automation through AI-based decision-making and network digital twins [38] [37].

2.4.2 R&D initiatives

iTrust6G benefits from collaborations with key research and development initiatives, ensuring that the project's solutions are forward-looking and aligned with the industry's evolving needs. The Hexa-X project, a European initiative for 6G development, focuses on creating foundational technologies, including AI-driven network management, which align closely with iTrust6G's goals [39]. Hexa-X provides critical insights into how AI can be used not only for network performance optimization but also for enhancing security by

enabling autonomous threat detection, analysis, and response across the 6G infrastructure.

In addition, iTrust6G builds upon the outcomes of 5G PPP projects such as 5G-VINNI and 5G-EVE [40] [41]. These projects have explored the secure orchestration of virtualized network functions (VNFs), which are expected to play a pivotal role in 6G. VNFs allow for flexible, scalable, and cost-efficient deployment of network services, but their reliance on virtualization introduces new attack vectors. iTrust6G focuses on securing VNFs throughout their lifecycle, from deployment to runtime, to ensure that the dynamic nature of 6G does not compromise security. Furthermore, AI-driven NFV is being explored to further automate and secure the virtualization processes, with insights drawn from related surveys and studies in the area [42] [43].

Privacy-preserving technologies are another critical aspect of iTrust6G's R&D efforts. One promising technology is federated learning, where AI models are trained across decentralized devices without aggregating sensitive data. This method ensures that sensitive user information remains localized, reducing the risk of data breaches while still enabling the network to learn from distributed datasets to improve security. This approach is particularly important for applications like IoT, where massive numbers of devices generate sensitive data across geographically dispersed locations. In parallel, homomorphic encryption is being investigated to perform secure computations on encrypted data, ensuring that sensitive information is never exposed, even when analysed [44] [45].

2.4.3 Standardization

Standardization plays a pivotal role in ensuring the widespread adoption and applicability of the iTrust6G security framework. To that end, iTrust6G actively engages with several major standardization bodies to ensure that its innovations are aligned with global best practices. One of the key areas of collaboration is with ETSI ZSM, where iTrust6G contributes to security aspects related to closed-loop automation and AI-driven network management. ZSM's focus on automation aligns directly with iTrust6G's vision of leveraging AI to automate security processes, such as threat detection, response, and remediation. By contributing to the development of ZSM standards, iTrust6G ensures that its solutions will be compatible with future 6G networks on a global scale [46] [37].

iTrust6G is also involved with ETSI NFV, where it works closely with the NFV REL WG and NFV SEC WG. These groups provide essential guidelines for securing virtualized environments, which are increasingly important as 6G networks rely more heavily on virtualized network functions. iTrust6G's alignment with these groups ensures that its security solutions are not only effective in preventing attacks but also resilient in maintaining service availability and performance during potential security incidents [42].

In addition, the project collaborates with ETSI SAI (Securing Artificial Intelligence) to address the unique challenges of securing AI systems. AI plays a central role in 6G, particularly in managing and optimizing network operations. However, AI systems are vulnerable to adversarial attacks, where malicious actors attempt to manipulate AI models to produce incorrect results [36]. By working with ETSI SAI, iTrust6G contributes to the development of standards that focus on safeguarding AI models from such attacks and ensuring that AI systems can enhance network security without becoming a point of vulnerability themselves [43].

Through its active participation in these standardization bodies, iTrust6G ensures that its security innovations are aligned with global industry practices, increasing the likelihood of widespread adoption and implementation in 6G networks.

3 iTrust6G Zero-Trust Concept

Since the digitalisation is impacting an ever-increasing part of daily life, connectivity and supporting network have become a daily necessity and support critical activities and have become a vital asset. For instance, energy, transport, finance and public administration are recognised by NIS2 [47] legislative framework as essential entities having to comply with the constraint of resilience, while heavily relying on telecommunications. Given the importance of the service they deliver, network infrastructure must be accepted and trusted by their users.

However, as the 6th generation of mobile networks is anticipated arising around 2030 [48], several fundamental paradigm changes is foreseen hampering the trust in the resources. Specifically,

- The **openness** of the network, due to the (i) API-ification of the network capabilities to third-party services and (ii) the increased involvement of diversified solution providers (including open-source communities). This situation exposes the network to the composition and interaction with software having a different degree of resilience and robustness.
- The **involvement of multiple providers**, providing and supervising their own network segment accounting for access network, transport technologies to be dynamically integrated to ensure constant and optimal connectivity (corresponding to the network of the network paradigm). This understands the involvement of actors enforcing different security management, which requires different trust model to cooperate.
- The **cloudification of the network services** and their continuous desegregation throughout the cloud continuum will increase the dynamism of applications deployment and the providers' resource usage. This dynamism will make it infeasible to establish a clear boundary for network service and therefore outwitting any attempts for a perimeter-based security approach.

Given this setting, iTrust6G proposes to adapt the ZT paradigm to build an End-to-End security architecture for trustworthy 6G networks. At its core, ZT architectures evaluate the current posture of subject willing to interact with a class of objects to grant them access on a per session need and with the least privilege. In the context of 6G networks, iTrust6G propose to control the connection establishment and network service deployment between different network services depending upon different providers. With this objective, iTrust6G aims at enacting the network layer to autonomously deliver an end-to-end trust connectivity to vertical applications. In this setting:

- In ZTA, “**subjects**” refer to network functions and provider’s domain that aims to contact a service situated in the administrative domain of a different provider.
- The term “**object**” refers to network functions that are in the domains of other providers, which the "subject" aims to access.
- The **action** to authorise or deny is the establishment of connections, including the deployment of supporting network services if needed for resource exploitation.

The chain of trust in 6G telecommunication appears by assimilating each administrative domain in interactions to provide communication capacity as a subject trying to interact with another one and iterating later. This way, each domain is a scrutinised subject for from the perspective of another domain having security and trust requirements, and every accepted connection is the result of a successful trust evaluation. Moreover, to provide confidence not only in the communication but also on how the system behaves, iTrust6G ensure that each decision autonomously taken by the system is not only accountable by explainable to enact introspection by a human auditor. That is how iTrust6G claims to establish an end-to-end ZT security platform for the next generation of mobile networks, as illustrated in Figure 3-1.

Figure 3-1: Overview of iTrust6G's concept for End-to-End trusted connectivity in 6G networks

The remaining major question arising to clarify the alignment with ZT paradigm is the properties of the provider's domains serving its current trust evaluation. To that end, we evaluate the domain providers under the following questions:

- *Are the providers of the domain cooperative in its trust assessment?*

In practice, we evaluate the capacity of a domain participate in a generation process, and its consumption for proactive mitigation. The gathered TI serves a trust indicator.

- *Is the supply chain and the infrastructure resource supporting network services tampered?*

Ensure that all hardware and software components in your supply chain are from trusted sources. Use digital signatures and checksums to verify the integrity of these components.

- *What is the current security posture of the domain, and how capable is it to mitigate vulnerabilities and remediate cyberthreats?*

Examples of this can be the answers for the following questions:

- Is there an inventory of all hardware, software, and data within the domain?
- Are assets regularly updated with the latest patches and versions?
- Are access controls properly implemented (e.g., least privilege principle)?
- Are authentication methods secure (e.g., multi-factor authentication)?
- Are there robust firewalls, intrusion detection/prevention systems, and network segmentation in place?
- Is traffic encrypted both at rest and in transit?

Based on these indicators, iTrust6G's adopted ZTA vision is expected to benefit the following groups:

- **End users** that can ensure robust and resilient communication;

- **Network service providers** that can ensure collaborating with trustworthy partners being confidently re-evaluated on a short timespan;
- **Infrastructure providers** (neutral hosts and cloud providers), that are minimizing their infrastructure’s exposure to attack vectors;
- **Application and content providers** that can refocus their security design and evaluation on business-logic process;
- **Security solution providers** that can be predictably committing their solution to the trust evaluation in network service providers.

Table 3-1 details how iTrust6G approach for ZT satisfies the tenets promoted by NIST [37].

Table 3-1 ZTA Tenets Fulfilment in iTrust6G Concept

#	ZT Tenet	Followed in iTrust6G?	Justification
1	All data sources and computing services are considered resources.	Yes	All network functions taking part in the platform are scrutinised and evaluated when initiating a connection with another domain.
2	All communication is secured regardless of network location	Yes	All network function to establish a connection must meet security criteria to be deemed trustworthy.
3	Access to individual enterprise resources is granted on a per-session basis.	Mostly	The access to administrative domain is controlled for network functions. User equipment’s are controlled indirectly via the network functions in interaction with them.
4	Access to resources is determined by dynamic policy- including the observable state of the client identity, application/service, the requesting asset – and may include other behavioural and environmental attributes	Yes	iTrust6G shall provide an intent-based policy framework to define security management, trust assessment strategy, and access control. Trust assessments account for static and dynamic attributes reflecting the design and the current state of a network function.
5	The enterprise monitor and measures the integrity and security posture of all owned and associated assets.	Mostly	The scrutinization covers the network function. Similarly to tenet #3, user equipment’s can be scrutinised indirectly via the network functions in interaction with them.
6	All resource authentication and authorisation are dynamic and strictly enforced before the system is allowed.	Yes	iTrust6G shall provide a policy decision tool capable of supporting dynamic requests. The policies will be highly granular, allowing for fine-tuned access control down to the data level. However, enforcing such decisions requires an adapted enforcement point, whose integration should be managed by the security policy.
7	The enterprise collects as much information as possible about the current state of assets, network infrastructure and communications and uses it to improve its security posture.	Yes	Security management shall incorporate dynamic threat detection and classification for dynamic countermeasure contributing to security posture, and therefore trust, maximisation.

4 Preliminary iTrust6G Architecture

This chapter outlines iTrust6G architecture and elaborates on the end-to-end trust connectivity concept. Firstly, an overview of the architecture is presented, detailing the main supporting pillars and involved actors. More detail on each individual component is then discussed by describing their mission and their expected interaction.

4.1 Architecture overview

The iTrust6G architecture is composed of five layers, each of having its own set of components and specific purpose to support ZT:

- **Collaborative threat intelligence layer** is the main pillar for coordinating trust evaluation among multiple tenants and provide the methods to exchange knowledge related to threat handling and trust evaluation. De facto, this layer benefits from the AI techniques used for cyberthreat intelligence generation from predicted incoming threat and permit to carry out proactive mitigation (Technical Objective 2 presented in the description of action document, and Section II of deliverable D2.1). This layer interacts with the "*static and trust assessment*" to provide knowledge used in the trust evaluation process (mainly through conformity) and is fed by forensic evidence strengthening share knowledge. It also interfaces with "*Security orchestration*" to share knowledge from threat referential used in vulnerability and threat detection, and CTI playbook involved in remediation.
- **Policy administration layer** acts as an administration and inspection point for domain administrator (e.g. Network service providers) willing to exploit iTrust6G platform, and it is therefore tenant specific. This layer permits the specification of intent-based security and trust policy and have explanation on its usages (Technical Objective 5). This layer interacts with the "*Static and Dynamic trust Assessment*" layer to (i) provide the trust and access control policies used for trust evaluation and (ii) receive identity attributes and access request logs for tamper-proof storage. This layer also interacts with the "*security orchestration*" to submit a security policy obtained from intent serving automation and collecting explanation for accountability purpose.
- **Static and dynamic trust assessment layer** serves the design of a trust management system serving the evaluation of posture of assets depending on their design (conformity to referential), their current posture (resource integrity and behaviour), and support forensic evidence (Technical Objective 3). This layer is therefore fundamental as part of a ZT architecture, as it is providing decisional capacity on access requests. Consequently, besides the interaction with the "*Collaborative Threat Intelligence*" and "*Policy Administration*" layers, it is natural for this layer to receive access requests addressed by the resources of the "*infrastructure*" layer, as well the listing of entities, and artefacts related to the RA, while reciprocally issuing Access decision and remote attestation requests on the infrastructure. Additionally, this layer interface with the "*Security Orchestration*" layer to transmit RA logs and trust evaluation serving to refine cyber-threat handling while collecting trust intelligence obtained from analysed security incidents. This layer is limited to one single tenant.
- **Security orchestration** layers supervise the several cyberthreat incident response process and integrate them with the adequate tooling for covering the clouds, edge, and extreme edge. Specifically, it instruments AI methodologies to automate decision-making in threat detection and classification while enabling the distribution in the administrative domain. Moreover, generative AI techniques are exploited to conduct the generation of remediation playbook adapted to the technical specificities of the resource needing protection at the level of the domain. The integration of tooling for collection of metrics and actuation capability is achieved by instrumenting dedicated programmability model altering the runtime of network functions (Technical Objective 4). Based the

interactions listed from all other components, the "Security Orchestration" naturally interacts with the infrastructure layer to constraints the service orchestration via security mechanisms to deploy, specific lifecycle action on network function & security mechanisms, and (re)-configuration actions. Reciprocally, this layer benefits from metrics & monitoring data used for vulnerability & threat detection. This layer is specific to a tenant.

- **Infrastructure layer** covers the traditional network resources (data plane, service instance), but augmented with additional embedded capacity from iTrust6G (e.g. security mechanisms serving enforcement, attested, isolation - Technical Objective 6). This layer intends to model uniformly the diverse type of technical environments anticipated for 6G (Softwarised RAN, edge nodes, core cloud network, data plane) to abstract the technical network complexity from iTrust6G platform's other layers. This layer is expected to be contiguous with other administrative domains involving other tenants and collaborate with them to service the operation of telecommunication applications.

Figure 4-1 outlines these layers and their different interactions.

4.2 Component descriptions

In the remainder of this section, a review of each iTrust6G layer and their components are presented. Besides a technical description of the design, the novelty of each solution beyond state-of-the-art is also highlighted. In addition, further details on their input requirements and capabilities in information flows are described.

Figure 4-1: iTrust6G architecture, a high-level overview

Figure 4-2: Policy administration components and interaction flows

4.2.1 Policy administration

The Policy Administration plane is responsible for managing and defining the access control policies that govern how resources are accessed within. It is primarily used by administrators to create, update, and manage these policies. This plane works in coordination with other planes, such as the Policy Decision Plane, which evaluates requests based on the policies. A key function of the Policy Administration Plane is to log all policy changes and interactions, providing transparency and explainability for auditing and compliance. The components and interaction flows are illustrated in Figure 4-2.

4.2.1.1 Intent Processor

The Intent Processor plays a crucial role by bridging the gap between abstract policies and actionable system behaviour. It is responsible for interpreting policies that specify high-level goals or operational constraints and translating them into concrete tasks that the system can execute.

Table 4-1 Intent Processor Specifications

Module name	Intent processor
Component description	The Intent Processor is responsible for interpreting intents expressed by operators and users and translating them into actionable tasks for the system. It ensures that the autonomous system operates in accordance with these policies by dynamically determining the best way to fulfil them using available solution artifacts.
Responsible partner	TID
Addressed scientific locks and novelty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> How can conflicting policies be autonomously resolved within the system? How can the system ensure that policy-based requests are aligned with available solution artifacts? How can the system handle policies that require capabilities it does not yet support? How does the system balance multiple, potentially conflicting policies with limited resources?
Interfaces	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ad-InP: Administrator and the Intent Processor InP-AcLe: Intent Processor and Accounting Ledger InP-PDP: Intent Processor and PDP InP- SD: Intent Processor and Static and Dynamic trust assessment layer

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • InP – RA: Intent Processor and risk assessment • InP–ReM: Interface between the Intent Processor and remediation manager • InP–RA: Intent Processor and risk assessment
Input required	Policy: The component receives policies, which express high-level goals, requirements, or constraints for the system.
Output produced	<p>Static and Dynamic trust assessment, risk assessment component/Security Orchestration/PDP: The output includes the necessary system actions and configurations derived from processed policies.</p> <p>Accounting ledger: The ledger receives traces of the elicited actions and configuration collected from the processed policies.</p> <p>Remediation manager: Security policy impacting the constraints on remediation selection.</p>
Related task(s)	T2.3

4.2.1.2 Explainability

The Explainability component plays a critical role in autonomous systems by providing transparency into the system’s decision-making processes. As autonomous systems increasingly manage complex tasks, it becomes essential for human operators and stakeholders to understand why and how these systems arrive at decisions or actions.

Table 4-2 Explainability Component Specifications

Module name	Explainability
Component description	The Explainability component is designed to provide insights into the decision-making processes of autonomous systems. It aims to make the actions, choices, and outcomes of these systems understandable to human operators.
Responsible partner	TID
Addressed scientific locks and novelty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How can an autonomous system's decisions be made comprehensible to human operators without oversimplifying the underlying complexity? • What mechanisms ensure that explanations of decisions maintain transparency while also being accessible to non-technical users?
Interfaces	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ex-Ad: Interface between the Explainability component and the end user (administrator). • Ex-AcL: Interface between the Explainability component and the accounting ledger.
Input required	Accounting ledger: The Explainability component requires access to the decisions made by the autonomous system, including the underlying policies, rules, models, and data sources that informed those decisions.
Output produced	User: The Explainability component produces clear, concise reports or real-time explanations that detail the decision-making process.
Related task(s)	T2.3

4.2.2 Collaborative threat intelligence

The Collaborative Threat Intelligence (CTI) plane is responsible for facilitating the secure, efficient, and scalable sharing of threat intelligence within the iTrust6G environment as illustrated in Figure 4-3. By leveraging multiple data sources, the plane aims to create a unified and robust defence against cyber adversaries.

Figure 4-3: CTI components and interaction flows

4.2.2.1 CTI Platform

The CTI component plays a critical role in collecting, analysing, and disseminating threat intelligence to help the rest of iTrust6G components understand, detect, and respond to cyber threats. The platform shall support the aggregation of information from various sources, process it into actionable insights, and integrate it into the iTrust6G security operations to improve defences and incident response.

Table 4-3 CTI Platform Specifications

Module name	CTI platform
Component description	The platform shall act as the centralised repository to collect, manage, and share threat intelligence. It will play a crucial role in normalizing, analysing, and distributing intelligence in real-time.
Responsible partner	NTUA
Addressed scientific locks and novelty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> How can we secure that the gathered intelligence will be complete, consistent, and up to date? How can we overcome the difficulties in mapping large volumes of threat data to maximise their contextual understanding? How can we secure the seamless integration of the diverse threat intelligence sources without extensive preprocessing? Does the platform share the information early enough to support detection and response capabilities? How human dependence can be reduced?
Interfaces	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CP-ETD: Interface between the CTI platform and the External threat DB CP-FA: Interface between the CTI platform and the Forensic Analyser CP-SDTC: Interface between the CTI platform and the Security threat and detection & classification component. CP-Tri: Interface between the CTI platform and the Trust Inference CP-ReM: Interface between the Remediation Manager and the CTI platform. CP-RA: Interface between the Risk Assessment component and the CTI platform.
Input required	Security threat detection & classification component: Indicators of Compromise (IoCs).

	<p>Forensics Analyser: IoCs, malware samples and signatures. Actual malware files or their unique identifiers that can be analysed for deeper understanding of the threat. Network traffic patterns: Suspicious network communication patterns associated with known threats.</p> <p>External Threat Database: The STIX v2.1 open-source threat intelligence information, and external threat intelligence feeds external Information regarding active threats, including IoCs and attack techniques, recommendations, etc.</p>
Output produced	<p>Security Monitoring & pre-detection, Trust Inference, Risk assessment component: Provision of threat intelligence comprising:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Indicators of Compromise (IoCs) • Structured Threat Information [e.g. in TAXII, STIX, CSV, JSON] • Sigma or Yara rules • Reports <p>Remediation manager: CTI information (level of details needed to be defined during the implementation)</p> <p>Risk assessment: CTI Information for risk evaluation.</p>
Related task(s)	T3.2

4.2.2.2 Remediation playbook repository

This component stores abstract remediation procedures that have been vetted by security practitioners or validated through practical experience with past incidents. These procedures may be shared across tenants, so no additional operational or private information is stored. Remediations can be catalogued according to enabling constraints, such as their features, including the security capabilities required to enforce them, the information needed to execute them correctly, and the type of healing they perform.

Table 4-4 Remediation Playbook Repository Specifications

Module name	Remediation playbook repository
Component description	<p>This repository contains the formal representations of all the remediation strategies available to the Remediation Selection and Enforcement Component to react to security relevant events. These strategies are generic, they describe the actions to perform, but they need to be tailored to the actual information system. This component will interact with the component responsible of generating the actual playbooks that will be used to enforce the reaction in the target system.</p>
Responsible partner	POLITO
Addressed scientific locks and novelty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How to define a format representing strategies abstractly and able to be interpretable by the component in charge for actualizing them? • How to interaction with de-facto standard, potential extensions, are also open questions, even if not relevant from the research point of view?
Interfaces	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ReP-RA: Interface between the Remediation Playbook repository, and the risk assessment components. • ReP- ReM- Interface between the Remediation Playbook repository, and the Remediation Manager.
Input required	<p>Remediation manager: Initially, the strategies will be defined manually, the knowledge of the use cases and the project scope is enough. In later versions of the iTrust6G framework, we will investigate the use of genAI to suggest additional strategies.</p>
Output produced	<p>Risk assessment component: This component is a repository. It can return in output what the stored playbooks.</p> <p>Remediation manager: the strategies for remediation will be put at the disposal of security orchestration for enacting remediation.</p>

Related task(s)	T3.3
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4.2.2.3 External threat database

The external cybersecurity threat intelligence database will serve as a knowledge repository (for the implementation needs of T3.2 and T5.2) that will contain data from external open-source cybersecurity threat intelligence sources. These data will be correlated with findings from the *Security Threat Detection Component* (related to T3.2), and the *Security Threat Monitoring* (related to T5.2).

Table 4-5 External Threat Database Specifications

Module name	External threat database
Component description	This component will serve as an open-source cybersecurity threat intelligence knowledge repository that will be utilized from components in order to correlate, aggregate, and enhance cybersecurity findings with extra cybersecurity information originating from open-source vendors.
Responsible partner	ADR
Addressed scientific locks and novelty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> How to design graph-based databases to facilitate the correlation of cybersecurity findings?
Interfaces	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CP-ETD: Interface between the CTI platform and the External threat DB SA-ETD: Interface between the External threat DB and the Static trust assessment component. ETD-SDTC: Interface between the External threat DB and the Security threat and detection & classification component. ETD-SeMo: Interface between the External threat DB and the Security Monitoring & pre-detection.
Input required	External open-source cybersecurity threat intelligence vendors (not in the scope of iTrust6G architecture): Certain CVE associations from the National Vulnerability Database related to the cybersecurity attacks that the <i>threat monitoring and pre-detection component</i> and <i>threat detection and classification component</i> will correlate with, and MITRE ATTACK framework, from which mild recommendation remediation actions will be derived from.
Output produced	<p>Threat monitoring & pre-detection component, threat detection & classification component: prediction, and knowledge correlated with already detected cybersecurity threats.</p> <p>CTI Platform: Possible integration with the STIX v2.1 open-source threat intelligence information sharing standard so that the information shared is consistent throughout the components.</p> <p>Static trust assessment component: list of vulnerabilities affecting software assets.</p>
Related task(s)	T3.2, T5.2

4.2.3 Trust model and evaluation

One goal is to design a remote attestation engine that leverages hardware root of trust to evaluate the integrity and runtime of network service instances. Another key focus is assessing the software design by using established security frameworks and cyber-threat intelligence to derive relevant trust metrics. AI techniques are also employed to dynamically evaluate the trustworthiness of network services in the 6G platform. Additionally, authentication methods and trust-based contextual information will be integrated to securely manage access from third-party applications to 6G resources. Figure 4-5 show the components and interaction flow of this module.

Figure 4-4: Trust model and evaluation components, and the interaction flows

4.2.3.1 Static trust assessment

The Static Trust Assessment component will evaluate the conformity of devices, and the evaluation of the security of software supply-chain aspects of the deployed services, within the network premises based on a specific policy that will be created explicitly for such networks (6G, O-RAN). This assessment will provide a trust score that can then be evaluated by other components within WP4.

Table 4-6 Static Trust Assessment Specifications

Module name	Static trust assessment
Component description	Assesses the security compliance of the devices within the 6G network. Assesses the supply-chain security of services used by those devices. The static trust assessment periodically evaluates the devices for their security compliance (both security policy and supply-chain aspects), produces a trust score and forwards to the AI trust evaluator (supported by T4.2 and T3.4).
Responsible partners	ADR, i2CAT
Addressed scientific locks and novelty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> As 6G/O-RAN networks do not have standardized compliance/conformity tests, how to create a set of security referential that will assess the trust of devices and services within 6G networks?
Interfaces	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> SA-ETD: Interface between the External threat DB and the Static trust assessment component. SA-SO: Interface between the Service Orchestrator and the Static trust assessment component. SA-ATE: Interface between the AI Trust Evaluator and the Static trust assessment

	component
Input required	External Threat Database: Provision of known vulnerabilities susceptible to affect the supply-chain of the services on the devices. Service Orchestrator: A list of the available devices and their services, and information about their composition.
Output produced	AI trust evaluator: Compliance Check Score, or Status (Score should be a numerical value, Status will be a state value of pass or not pass). This will be considered as a static trust indicator and would be consumed by the AI Trust Evaluator.
Related task(s)	T4.1

4.2.3.2 AI trust evaluator module

The AI Trust Evaluator Module is a critical component in the iTrust6G project, responsible for assessing and quantifying the trustworthiness of devices, and network functions within the 6G environment. This component plays a pivotal role in enhancing the security and reliability of the 6G network infrastructure by providing dynamic trust scores that influence network orchestration and security policy decisions.

Table 4-7 AI Trust Evaluator Module Specifications

Module name	AI trust evaluator module
Component description	The AI Trust Evaluator Module is responsible for fusing and analysing signals from multiple sources to determine a quantitative trust score for nodes, devices, and network functions within the iTrust6G platform. It ingests data from remote attestation, trust inference reports and security and infrastructure events. Using advanced AI/ML techniques, it correlates and analyses this multi-modal data to calculate a "DEFCON-like" trust score that represents the current security posture and trustworthiness of the evaluated entity. This dynamic trust score is then used by other components, particularly the network infrastructure orchestrator, to adjust security policies and resource allocation based on the perceived trust level.
Responsible partners	PDM & POLITO
Addressed scientific locks and novelty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How can we effectively fuse heterogeneous security signals to produce a meaningful trust score? • What AI/ML techniques are most suitable for correlating diverse security data sources? • How do we account for the temporal aspects and potential inconsistencies in multi-source security data? • How can we design a trust scoring system that is both granular and actionable for network orchestration? • How do we ensure the AI models themselves are trustworthy and resilient to adversarial manipulation?
Interfaces	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SA-ATE: Interface between the AI Trust Evaluator and the Static trust assessment component. • ATE-RAE: Interface between the AI Trust Evaluator and the Remote attestation engine. • ATE-ReM: Interface between the AI Trust Evaluator and the Remediation Manager. • ATE-TrI: Interface between the AI Trust Evaluator and the Trust Inference. • ATE- AcLe: Interface between the AI Trust Evaluator and the accounting ledger/Evidence repository. • ATE-SeMo: Interface between the AI Trust Evaluator and the security monitoring and pre-detection
Input required	Static trust assessment: Compliance Check Score, or Status of the assets Remote attestation engine: Integrity measurements and attestation results as

	<p>events.</p> <p>Trust Inference: provides <i>Trust Intelligence</i> which is data that encapsulates contextual information for trust evaluation</p> <p>Security monitoring and pre-detection: Security events from Security Information and Event Management (SIEM).</p>
Output produced	<p>Remediation manager: trust evaluation containing the dynamic trust scores for nodes/devices/functions for <i>Network Infrastructure</i> and Trust-based policy recommendations for <i>Security Policy Engine</i>.</p> <p>Explainability & accounting ledger: Insights and suggestions for the Security Policy Engine to optimize security policies based on inferred trust levels.</p> <p>Evidence repository & accounting ledger: Trust Information & trust scores.</p>
Related task(s)	T4.2 & T3.4

4.2.3.3 Remote attestation engine

A Remote Attestation Engine is a security component that verifies the integrity and trustworthiness of a remote system by validating its hardware and software configurations. It typically uses cryptographic techniques to generate and send evidence, such as a system's state or measurements, to a trusted verifier, which then checks this data against known good values. This ensures that the remote system has not been tampered with and is running in a trusted state.

Table 4-8 Remote Attestation Engine Specifications

Module name	Remote attestation engine
Component description	The Remote Attestation Engine collects and verifies integrity measurements of a system's hardware, firmware, and software. It challenges attesters to provide integrity proofs, compares them with reference values, and generates a report attesting the system's trustworthiness. The proofs generated by the attesters are protected using private keys stored in secure hardware. Those keys are registered to the Remote attestation Engine and bounded to the attester identity.
Responsible partner	POLITO
Addressed scientific locks and novelty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> How can we ensure that the measurements of a system's hardware and software are accurate and tamper-proof? How do we handle attestation for dynamic systems where software and configurations are frequently updated? What strategies can be used to ensure privacy-preserving attestation while still providing enough information to the verifier?
Interfaces	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> RAE-SeMo: Interface between the Security Monitoring & pre-detection and the Remote attestation engine. ATE-RAE: Interface between the AI Trust Evaluator and the Remote attestation engine. RAE-FA: Interface between the forensic analyser and the Remote attestation engine. RAE-At: Interface between the Attester and the Remote attestation engine. RAE-SO: Interface between the Service Orchestrator and the Remote attestation engine.
Input required	<p>Service Orchestrator: Registration of entities that requires to be attested and expected values (expected configuration and applications running on the attested system), reference measurements.</p> <p>Attester: Remote attestation evidence.</p>
Output produced	Forensic Analyser, AI-trust-evaluator and Security monitoring & prediction components: Attestation report including the state of a component and eventually information regarding the unexpected events.

	Attester: Remote attestation requests.
Related task(s)	T4.2

4.2.3.4 Forensic analyser

The Forensic Analyser is responsible for generating insights on the effects of cybersecurity incidents on the monitored system. It uses inputs from affected system themselves and other monitoring tools such as logs and applies AI techniques to generate reports that describe the details of the incidents in a timeline, its effect on the system and provides insights on the attacker themselves.

Table 4-9 Forensic Analyser Specifications

Module name	Forensic analyser
Component description	The component shall assist the forensic investigation on 6G networks. It will consider WP3 AI methodologies for cyber threat intelligence generation and will further infer forensics from trust analysis based on certain properties of 6G resources. The output is used to piece together the sequence of events, determine the nature of an incident, and support decision-making.
Responsible partner	NTUA
Addressed scientific locks and novelty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How can we gather data from systems with low storage capacity? • How can we infer information from 6G systems during cybersecurity incidents? • How can we improve the forensic analysis process? • How can we automate the process and reduce the need for human input and manual analysis?
Interfaces	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RAE-FA: Interface between the forensic analyser and the Remote attestation engine. • CP-FA: Interface between the CTI platform and the Forensic Analyser. • FA-SeMo: Interface between the Security Monitoring & pre-detection module and the Forensic Analyser
Input required	<p>Remote Attestation engine: remote attestation logs.</p> <p>CTI Platform: CTI data, IOCs, TTPs, Vulnerabilities, etc.</p> <p>Security monitoring and pre-detection: data sources from the monitored system including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Network Traffic Logs • Device and User Authentication Logs • Virtualized Infrastructure Logs • Edge Computing Data • IoT Device Logs • Network Slice Data • Security Event Logs • Cloud Service Logs • AI Model Logs • Time Synchronization Data
Output produced	CTI Platform: A report with: (i) Artifacts and Evidence, (ii) Indicators of Compromise (IoCs), (iii) Timeline Analysis, (iv) Root Cause and Attack Vector and (v) Threat Actor Attribution and TTPs.
Related task(s)	T4.4

4.2.3.5 Identity provider

The Identity Provider (IdP) is a core component in modern authentication ecosystems, responsible for securely managing and validating user identities. Through protocols such as SAML, OAuth, and OpenID Connect, the IdP ensures seamless integration with various applications and services, enabling federated

identity management across distributed systems.

Table 4-10 Identity Provider Specifications

Module name	Identity provider (IdP)
Component description	The Identity Provider (IdP) component enables the secure authentication of users by verifying their identities and issuing authentication assertions to requesting applications or services. It supports federated identity management, allowing users to access multiple applications using a single set of credentials. The IdP handles identity proofing, credential validation, and session management while ensuring compliance with security and privacy standards such as OAuth 2.0, SAML 2.0, or OpenID Connect.
Responsible partner	TID
Addressed scientific locks and novelty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> How can user identities be securely verified across distributed systems while maintaining privacy? How can federated identity management be enhanced to ensure cross-platform interoperability?
Interfaces	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> IdP-AcLe: Interface between the IdP and the Accounting ledger. IdP-C: Interface between the IdP and the component which has been authenticated.
Input required	<p>User/Server: The IdP receives identity verification requests, including user credentials (such as username/password or tokens). The IdP adheres to standardized protocols like SAML, OAuth 2.0, and OpenID Connect for communication and validation.</p> <p>Security Mechanisms acting as Policy Enforcement Point (PEP): Information about user's compliance with policies.</p>
Output produced	<p>User/Server: After successful authentication, which also involves sending the user's information to the <i>PEP</i> to check whether the user complies with the previously established policies and to receive the decision taken by <i>PDP</i>, the IdP generates and transmits authentication assertions or tokens (e.g., <i>JSON Web Token (JWT)</i>). These tokens encapsulate information such as user identity, session information, and access permissions. The output adheres to industry standards like OAuth 2.0 to ensure interoperability and security.</p> <p>Security Mechanisms acting as PEP: Requesting user's information to assess its compliance with the <i>policy</i>.</p> <p>Accounting ledger: The IdP also sends to the "<i>Accounting ledger</i>" all the information about the authentication process and the decisions taken underneath.</p>
Related task(s)	T4.3

4.2.3.6 Policy decision point

The Policy Decision Point (PDP) is a critical component responsible for evaluating access request against defined policies to determine whether a user should be granted or denied access to a resource. It acts as the decision-making engine within an authorization system, receiving input from other components like the PEP and making dynamic, context-aware authorization decisions.

Table 4-11 Policy Decision Point Specifications

Module name	Policy decision point (PDP)
Component description	The Policy Decision Point (PDP) is designed to evaluate access requests based on predefined authorization policies and contextual factors, such as user roles, attributes, and environmental conditions. It processes requests from the <i>Policy Enforcement Point (PEP)</i> and applies granular, policy-based rules to determine access permissions. This ensures that users receive only the minimum access required (principle of least privilege), while also adapting decisions dynamically based on real-

	time conditions, such as device security status or behavioural anomalies. The <i>PDP</i> supports fine-grained access control, enabling precise and secure management of user access to sensitive resources.
Responsible partner	TID
Addressed scientific locks and novelty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How can policies be designed to support granular, least-privilege access while remaining scalable and adaptable to organizational changes? • How can we ensure that the <i>PDP</i> continues to function effectively under high loads or distributed environments?
Interfaces	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>PDP-AcLe</i>: Interface between the <i>PDP</i> and the Accounting ledger. • <i>EvR-PDP</i>: Interface between the <i>PDP</i> and the Evidence Repository. • <i>PDP-PEP/PDP-SO</i>: Interface between the <i>PDP</i> and the <i>PEP</i> (possibly through the security orchestrator). • <i>PDP-InP</i>: Interface between the <i>PDP</i> and the Intent Processor acting as Policy Administration Point.
Input required	<p>Security Mechanisms acting as <i>PEP</i>: The <i>PDP</i> receives access requests from the <i>PEP</i>, which include relevant user credentials, attributes, and contextual information. This input is evaluated against authorization policies that define who can access which resources under what conditions.</p> <p>Policies: The <i>PDP</i> receives authorization policies generated by the <i>Intent Processor</i>. These policies define access control rules, specifying which users can access which resources and under what circumstances, ensuring that access decisions align with organizational intent and compliance standards.</p> <p>Evidence repository: User activities, enabling the identification of whether their behavior is appropriate or inappropriate.</p>
Output produced	<p>Security Mechanisms acting as <i>PEP</i>: The <i>PDP</i> produces an authorization decision, which is then communicated back to the <i>PEP</i>. This decision states whether the user is allowed or denied access to the requested resource, based on the evaluated policies and contextual conditions.</p> <p>Accounting ledger: The <i>PDP</i> also sends to the “<i>Accounting ledger</i>” all information on the authorisation process and on the decisions that have been taken underneath.</p>
Related task(s)	T4.3

4.2.4 Security orchestration

The security orchestration layer oversees conducting day-to-day management operation to maintain the network platform in the optimal and secure state, strengthening the trustworthiness of the network application under the administrative platform. The main processes introduced by this layer relate to cyberthreat detection, classification and remediation, and risk detection and mitigation. The security orchestration layer operates within the constraints set by security policies from the policy administration plane. It also provides explanatory feedback on threat classifications. Furthermore, the knowledge and operational procedures for handling threats are shared with the collaborative Threat Intelligence (TI) layer. This sharing enables other administrative domains to effectively respond to similar cyber threats under the same conditions. The trust evaluation layer collaborates closely with other components to gather comprehensive information on the threat landscape. This collaboration involves obtaining data on the integrity of infrastructure nodes and exchanging details about the security and trust posture. Finally, this layer directly manages the infrastructure to supervise the security configuration of network service and ancillary enablers and obtain visibility over the current state of a deployment.

Figure 4-5: Security Management Components and Interaction flows

4.2.4.1 Security monitoring and pre-detection

The Security Monitoring and Pre-Detection component is a critical element of the iTrust6G security architecture, functioning as an advanced Security Information and Event Management (SIEM) system tailored for 6G environments. It provides comprehensive vulnerability detection, continuous monitoring, and proactive threat intelligence capabilities. This component collects and analyses data from various sources across the 6G network infrastructure to identify potential security risks, detect anomalies, and provide actionable insights for threat mitigation.

Table 4-12 Security Monitoring and Pre-Detection Specifications

Module name	Security monitoring and pre-detection
Component description	This component comprises a SIEM with permitting (i) the real-time log and event data collection from diverse 6G network elements, (ii) the correlation and analysis of security events using AI/ML algorithms, (iii) the vulnerability scanning and assessment for O-RAN and beyond 5G-specific systems. It shall integrate external threat intelligence feeds for detection purpose for automated alert generation and prioritization. Finally, a customizable dashboard for security visualization and reporting is made available.
Responsible partners	ADR & PDM
Addressed scientific locks and novelty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> How to develop a specialized detection algorithms for O-RAN and beyond 5G-specific cyberattacks in multi-vendor environments?

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How to integrate and correlate diverse threat intelligence sources for enhanced 6G security? • How to apply AI/ML techniques for anomaly detection and predictive threat analysis in 6G networks? • How to design of scalable SIEM architecture capable of handling massive data volumes generated by 6G networks?
Interfaces	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ETD-SeMo: Interface between the External threat DB and the Security Monitoring & pre-detection. • RAE-SeMo: Interface between the Security Monitoring & pre-detection and the Remote attestation engine. • FA-SeMo: Interface between the Security Monitoring & pre-detection module and the Forensic Analyser. • SeMo-SO: Interface between the Security Monitoring & pre-detection module and the Service Orchestrator. • SeMo-TrI: Interface between the Security Monitoring & pre-detection module and the Trust Inference component. • SeMo-SDTC: Interface between the Security Monitoring & pre-detection module and the Security Threat Detection and classification component.
Input required	<p>External threat DB: Data from External Threat Database (vulnerability CVEs).</p> <p>Service Orchestrator: Metrics & monitoring data (Network topology and asset inventory information from the orchestrator; IP, Device Hostname, MAC, Open Ports from the resource).</p> <p>RA Engine: RA Logs containing Remote attestation results and integrity measurement.</p>
Output produced	<p>Security threat detection & classification component: Detection metrics and security events containing real-time security alerts and incidents.</p> <p>Trust Inference: a threat situation report containing:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Detected vulnerabilities and associated remediation recommendations. • Threat intelligence reports and indicators of compromise (IoCs). • Security posture assessments and risk scores. • Compliance and audit reports. <p>The output will be formatted using the STIX v2.1 open-source threat intelligence information sharing standard to ensure consistency across components.</p> <p>AI Trust evaluator: Security events from Security Information and Event Management (SIEM).</p>
Related task(s)	T5.2

4.2.4.2 Security Threat Detection and Classification Component

The Security Threat Detection and Classification component will provide machine learning-based network monitoring capabilities that will detect and classify potential 5G-specific cyber network attacks.

Table 4-13 Security Threat Detection and Classification Component Specifications

Module name	Security threat detection and classification component
Component description	The component will provide machine learning-based network monitoring capabilities, as well as system log utilization, monitoring specific network segments and producing an alert if an attack is detected. Minor external cybersecurity open-source threat intelligence correlation will occur, if possible, to enhance the detected vulnerability knowledge.
Responsible partner	ADR
Addressed scientific locks and novelty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How to design and develop an attack detection system accounting for the decentralised and disaggregated nature of O-RAN networks? • How to detect & classify cyber-threats fostered by O-RAN’s open interface and

	increased vulnerability surface?
Interfaces	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CP-SDTC: Interface between the CTI platform and the Security threat and detection & classification component. • ETD-SDTC: Interface between the External threat DB and the Security threat and detection & classification component. • SeMo-SDTC: Interface between the Security Monitoring & pre-detection module and the Security Threat Detection and classification component. • SDTC-AcLe: Interface between the Account Ledger and the Security threat and detection & classification component. • SDTC-ReM: Interface between the Remediation Manager and the Security threat and detection & classification component. • SDTC-FLA: Interface between the federated learning models and aggregations, and the Security threat and detection & classification component.
Input required	<p>Forensic Analyser: Network Data (Netflow Data) & System Logs</p> <p>External Threat Database: External threat intelligence data (more specifically, vulnerabilities).</p> <p>Security Monitoring & pre-detection: Forecasting and understanding cybersecurity threats based on existing data and known vulnerabilities.</p>
Output produced	<p>Remediation Manager: Vulnerability Detection and Classification, and possible extra cybersecurity threat intelligence information regarding the discovered vulnerabilities.</p> <p>CTI Platform: Possible integration with the STIX v2.1 open-source threat intelligence information sharing standard so that the information shared is consistent throughout the components.</p> <p>Evidence repository & accounting ledger: Element for explanation on the decision made and especially on the side of vulnerabilities and security posture.</p>
Related task(s)	T3.2

4.2.4.3 Federated learning models

The federated learning component is an ancillary tooling assisting the security threat detection and classification component in the distribution of machine learning models used for the cyber-threat techniques detection and qualification.

Table 4-14 Federated Learning Models Specifications

Module name	Federated learning models
Component description	The Federated Learning component helps multiple remote parties to collaboratively train a single machine learning model without sharing data. Each party trains a local model with a private data set. Only the local model is sent to the aggregator to improve the quality of the global model that benefits all parties.
Responsible partner	NTUA
Addressed scientific locks and novelty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How to ensure that model updates are fully private and resistant to attacks? • How to reduce communication overhead while ensuring effective model updates? • How to manage data heterogeneity and device variability without sacrificing model performance or convergence speed? • How to secure that all clients can be trusted to participate in learning process?
Interface	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SDTC-FLA: Interface between the federated learning models and aggregations, and the Security threat and detection & classification component.
Input required	Security threat detection and classification component: The component works in close collaboration with the <i>security threat detection and classification component</i> (task 3.2). Settings like learning rate, batch size, and aggregation rules must be defined and the gradients or weights computed by clients after local training must

	be acquired.
Output produced	Security threat detection and classification component: Local model updates based on the aggregation rules.
Related task(s)	T3.1

4.2.4.4 Trust inference

The Trust Inference module is responsible for evaluating and quantifying the trustworthiness of entities within the iTrust6G system, including devices, network functions, and services.

Table 4-15 Trust Inference Specifications

Module name	Trust Inference
Component description	The Trust Inference Module integrates into the security orchestration framework to analyse contextual information from various security indicators, thereby inferring the trust posture of network entities. The Trust Inference Module collects and processes raw security data from various sources, including indicators of compromise (IoCs), cyber threat intelligence (CTI), raw security data and others. It produces an intermediate trust intelligence, which serves as a foundational input for dynamic trust assessment and subsequent trust score computation. This report contains contextual information and initial trust indicators but does not produce final trust scores. It serves as a data aggregation and pre-processing step.
Responsible partner	PDM
Addressed scientific locks and novelty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How to ensure that AI models used for trust inference are resilient to adversarial manipulations and maintain trustworthy performance? • How to securely collect and aggregate trust-relevant data from diverse sources? • How can we incorporate zero trust architecture principles to enable constant evaluation of communication between nodes participating in threat intelligence processes?
Interfaces	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CP-Trl: Interface between the CTI platform and the Trust Inference • ATE-Trl: Interface between the AI Trust Evaluator and the Trust Inference. • SeMo-Trl: Interface between the Security Monitoring & pre-detection module and the Trust Inference component.
Input required	CTI Platform: Threat indicators and security alerts. Security Monitoring & Pre-Detection: System logs and metrics, network telemetry data. Vulnerability scan results and risk assessments. This should also include logs from third Party Applications, such as (Application behaviour and access patterns).
Output produced	AI trust evaluator: Trust Intelligence containing aggregating and pre-processed security data that encapsulates contextual information for trust evaluation.
Related task(s)	T3.4

4.2.4.5 Remediation manager

This component supervises the elicitation and enforcement processes of the remediation strategy against detected threats and risk. This process includes (i) the generation of adequate playbooks, (ii) the selection of adequate security mechanism to be deployed supporting the execution of this playbook, (iii) their execution against the service orchestrator's NBI and (iv) the storage of obtain playbooks to a shared repository as part of an intelligence.

Table 4-16 Remediation Manager Specifications

Module name	Remediation manager
Component description	This component is in charge for identifying the remediation to enforce when security

	<p>relevant information (e.g., incidents, suspicious activities, new vulnerabilities) is identified by other components managing and enriching CTI.</p> <p>It receives the security relevant information, possibly collects additional data for making decisions, and identifies the suitable remediation strategies. Initially, the strategies will be rated for their effectiveness with experts' judgments. Later version of the iTrust6G framework will see this component interact with the Risk Assessment module to rate the impact of the proposed strategies.</p> <p>Once the remediation strategy is decided, this component transform the generic strategies into an actionable playbook that can be used to enforce the remediation in the target scenario.</p> <p>The operation of these enablers will be supported by specialised security enablers, to be selected and deployed from a catalogue according to the remediation's need and current posture of resources needing protections.</p>
Responsible partner	POLITO
Addressed scientific locks and novelty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How to infer the strategies to enforce based on CTI information? • How to be able to evaluate and assess remediation before enforcing on the actual scenario (i.e., making decisions based on risk analysis and risk profiles)? • How to contextualise abstract recipes for enforcing strategies beyond simple strategies to react to simple threats? How to devise sophisticated reactions to advanced threats? • How to confidently qualify and select security enablers needed for remediation strategy enactment?
Interfaces	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ReP- ReM: Interface between the Remediation Playbook repository, and the Remediation Manager. • ATE-ReM: Interface between the AI Trust Evaluator and the Remediation Manager. • SDTC-ReM: Interface between the Remediation Manager and the Security threat and detection & classification component. • ReM-SO: Interface between the Remediation Manager and the Service Orchestrator. • ReM-RA: Interface between the Remediation Manager and the Risk Assessment component. • InP-RM: Interface between the Intent Processor and remediation manager • CP-ReM: Interface between the Remediation Manager and the CTI platform.
Input required	<p>CTI Platform: CTI information (level of details needed to be defined during the implementation)</p> <p>Service Orchestrator: Description of the target scenario (e.g., network landscape/topology and assets, information about the capabilities owned by the security controls in there)</p> <p>Threat detection & classification components: Risk assessment evaluations as provided by other iTrust6G components, as a deviation of the current landscape.</p> <p>Risk assessment component: Risk profiles summarizing the risk assessment results. May be expressed with one or more scores.</p> <p>Remediation playbook repository: Retrieval of playbook implementing remediation strategies and sharable with other parties.</p> <p>Intent processor: Security policy impacting the constraints on the remediation selection.</p>
Output produced	<p>Service Orchestrator: Abstract strategies proposed to mitigate the security relevant events. Selected strategy and its actualization obtained as contextualization to the target scenario. Output is expected to be sent to the service Orchestrator NBI. Implementation of the security mechanism serving the implementation.</p> <p>Risk assessment component: Concrete remediations to enable the risk assessment</p>

	component to complementing data for the risk mitigation estimate computations. Remediation playbook repository: Storage of playbooks implementing remediation strategies and sharable with other parties.
Related task(s)	T5.4

4.2.4.6 Risk assessment component

This component predicts the impacts of remediation measures on the security postures of resources to protect, gauging their effectiveness.

Table 4-17 Risk Assessment Component Specifications

Module name	Risk assessment component
Component description	<p>This component is in charge for assessing the cybersecurity risks in the operational environment. This component knows the target scenario, its risks, and the already deployed mitigations. A risk analysis performed offline is needed for this component to work. It should include assets and their values, threat and attacker models, and deployed security controls.</p> <p>This information is needed to produce one or more risk scores that summarize the current exposure of the target scenario to cybersecurity risks. When CTI information is provided as input, this component re-evaluates the risk scores. This information can be used by other components to start a remediation process.</p> <p>Moreover, it can receive as input actionable remediations, estimate the impacts on the target scenario and reevaluate the risks after the remediations are enforced. These scores are provided to components managing reactions to decide the most effective remediations.</p>
Responsible partner	POLITO
Addressed scientific locks and novelty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How to integrate static risk management information with dynamic risk evaluation based on CTI and proposed changes? • How to determine automatically if the information needed by the component to assess risks needs to be complemented with information directly sensed from the target scenario (e.g., with a vulnerability scanner)? • Can risk assessment methodology be used for continuous monitoring (e.g., performance-wise, its impact in the network standard behaviour)?
Interfaces	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ReP-RA: Interface between the Remediation Playbook repository, and the risk assessment component. • InP-RA: Intent Processor and risk assessment • ReM-RA: Interface between the Remediation Manager and the Risk Assessment component. • RA-AcLe: Interface between the Risk Assessment component and accounting ledger. • CP-RA: Interface between the Risk Assessment component and the CTI platform. • ReM-RA: Interface between the Remediation Manager and the Risk Assessment component.
Input required	<p>CTI Platform & External Threat database: This component will make use of CTI produced by the dedicated components of the framework. Both of internal and external type, with the first furnishing evidence of a certain event, and the second as correlation with threat modelling reference frameworks, e.g., MITRE ATT&CK. This information is retrieved from a CTI platform.</p> <p>Remediation Playbook Repository: Moreover, this component may retrieve abstract remediations stored in the Remediation Playbook Repository.</p> <p>Remediation Manager: This component also accounts for concrete remediations</p>

	from the Remediation Manager, complementing data for the risk mitigation estimate computations. Intent processor: Security policy impacting the risk evaluation weights
Output produced	Remediation Manager: Risk profiles summarizing the risk assessment results. May be expressed with one or more scores. Accounting ledger: elements from risk profiles serving the explanations.
Related task(s)	T3.3

4.2.5 Infrastructure

The infrastructure layer of iTrust6G is responsible from managing the network entities and services including the data and control plane for example in a telecom operator cloud which is compliant with the administrative domain in a secure, robust and reliable manner. It involves creation, management and termination of resources or network services along with their security mechanisms involving a secure service orchestrator along with security mechanisms from Security Orchestrator complemented by programmable security mechanisms and trust values or information from Static and Dynamic Trust assessment component. This layer will also involve remote attester for the network entities or services contributing to the trust assessment. Furthermore, the infrastructure layer provides metrics and monitoring data to the security orchestration layer for continuous assessment and asset listings and reference measurements to the Trust assessment layer.

4.2.5.1 Programmable security Mechanisms and policy enforcement points

The programmable security mechanisms are serving as pervasive security monitoring and control. They serve the (i) gathering of metrics for risk, threat and trust evaluation and (ii) provide actuation capability, possibly acting Policy-enforcement points. Those mechanisms are single-purposed and supervised by the service orchestrator and the remediation and enforcement components.

Figure 4-6: Infrastructure-level components and interaction flows

Table 4-18 Programmable Security Mechanisms Specifications

Module name	Programmable security mechanisms and Policy Enforcement Points
Component description	This conceptual component refers to monitoring and control elements in the resource needing protection. They represent containerised network functions or application library, or software modules in kernel space in specific providing specific security features. They expose an interface to actuate and monitor part or the entirety of a network service. In the context of access control and ZT paradigm implementation, those components can implement the capabilities of Policy Enforcement Point (PEP) to solicit access control decision and enforce them accordingly, to mitigate access to network resources in compliance with the proposed access control policy.
Responsible partners	I2CAT, PDM, ADR, TID
Addressed scientific locks and novelty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How to increase the observability of resources to satisfy to increase the confidence in security management and trust evaluation? • How to incorporate security and trust constraints in the design of vulnerable resources to leverage security-by-design? • How to manage security enabler lifecycle to maximise the utility of protected resources while maintaining an agreed level of security? • How to confidently enforce access control decision issued for ZT management?
Interface	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PrSe-SO: Interface between the Service Orchestrator and the Programmable Security Mechanism. • PrSe-NS: Interface between the Network Service and the Programmable Security Mechanism.
Input required	Service Orchestrator, Policy Decision Point: A technical security configuration serving to configure a mechanism and actuate, and/or an access control decision to accept or deny an action under the control of the mechanism.
Output produced	Service Orchestrator, Policy Decision Point: A flow of security data used for threat detection in security orchestration (and indirectly trust evaluation), the specification of an access request from an entity of the data plane able to be monitored by the mechanism.
Related task(s)	T5.1, T5.2, T4.3

4.2.5.2 Network services

The entities of the iTrust6G platform that will be implemented could be considered as network services. Those services will focus on AI-driven threat intelligence, intelligent trust management, and AI-enabled security orchestration and programmability.

Table 4-19 Network Services Specifications

Module name	Network services
Component description	The network services will not be considered as a component per se, rather than a general description and definition of the components of the iTrust6G infrastructure. In practice, they are expected to represent software and hardware payload in compliance with reference network standards (e.g. ETSI's Physical/Containerised/Virtualised network functions, O-RAN's xAPP/rAPP). Those entities could be the components to be implemented to fulfil the needs of the iTrust6G pilots.
Responsible partners	ADR, PDM, POLITO, TID, NTUA, i2CAT, LEN
Addressed scientific locks and novelty	No scientific novelties exist within this description, as this component is expected to represent a typical use-case.
Interfaces	PrSe-NS: Interface between the Network Service and the Programmable Security Mechanism.

	NS-SO: Interface between the Network Service and the Service Orchestrator.
Input required	Service Orchestrator: Day-0 and Day-1 configuration. We omit the role of the infrastructure orchestrator in the day-to-day management of this resource.
Output produced	Service Orchestration: Optionally, the service orchestrator can receive operation metrics from the resources. We omit the role of the infrastructure orchestrator in the day-to-day management of this resource.
Related task(s)	T6.3

4.2.5.3 Attester

The attester application is a component in the remote attestation process responsible for collecting, measuring, and reporting the state of a system's software, firmware, and hardware. It runs on the system being attested, often leveraging trusted hardware such as a TPM to gather cryptographically secure measurements. These measurements, which reflect the system's current state, are then signed and sent to a remote verifier for validation. The attester ensures that these reports are protected from tampering, providing proof that the system is in a trustworthy state before any sensitive operations or interactions occur.

Table 4-20 Attester Specifications

Module name	Attester
Component description	The Attester Application is responsible for securely measuring and reporting the integrity of a system's hardware, firmware, and software during the remote attestation process. It interacts with trusted hardware, such as a TPM or secure enclave, to collect cryptographically signed integrity measurements. The attester ensures that all reported data is protected from tampering, providing cryptographic evidence of the system's current state to verify its trustworthiness before sensitive operations are permitted. Requires trusted hardware on the platform such as TPM.
Responsible partner	POLITO
Addressed scientific locks and novelty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How keys for attestation are generated, linked to the attester and registered to the verifier? • How can the attester securely collect and measure system components without exposing itself to potential attacks?
Interfaces	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RAE-At: Interface between the Attester and the Remote attestation engine. • At-Inf: Interface between the Attester and the Infrastructure.
Input required	Infrastructure: Configuration Data regarding verifier address and some system information (ip address) RA Engine: Remote attestation request to solicit an attestation.
Output produced	RA Engine: RA evidence in the shape of signed report of the system's software, firmware, and hardware state that will be consumed by the Attestation Engine
Related task(s)	T4.2

4.2.5.4 Infrastructure orchestrator

The infrastructure orchestrator is in charge of the management of lifecycle resources supporting the operation of network services. Essentially, this component is not expected to be delivered by iTrust6G project, but be taken off-the-shelves, as technological enabler implementing reference standard. For instance, Management and Orchestration (MANO) is a key architectural framework in Network Function Virtualization (NFV), which enables the management and orchestration of virtualized network functions (VNFs). MANO is defined by the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI) and is critical for deploying and managing virtualized network services in modern telecommunications networks, particularly in environments like 5G and beyond. MANO helps telecommunications operators and service providers transition from traditional,

hardware-based network services to software-based, agile network infrastructures. It provides the necessary framework to manage complex, distributed VNFs while maintaining network performance and reliability. O-RAN is also providing a reference architecture in softwarised radios, making it particularly attractive to address appliance operation at the extreme edge of the network. In this framework, the Service Management Orchestration Framework supervises the lifecycle of network function in near-real-time interaction with radio interface (xApp), or non-real-time (rApp).

Table 4-21 Infrastructure Orchestrator Specifications

Module name	Infrastructure orchestrator
Component description	The component shall facilitate the management and the orchestration (MANO) of network services (VNFs and CNFs) across various types of infrastructure.
Responsible partners	NTUA, TID, PDM
Addressed scientific locks and novelty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How can be ensured the interoperability of heterogeneous VNFs and CNFs? • How can be secured the communication between its components and the VIMs, secure onboarding of VNFs, and integrity checking throughout the lifecycle? • How to achieve seamless orchestration of both virtualized and containerized services? • How to ensure resource isolation and security without sacrificing performance (when dealing with multi-tenancy).
Interfaces	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SO-InO: Interface between the Service Orchestrator and the Infrastructure Orchestrator. • InO-Inf: Interface between the orchestrator and the Infrastructure.
Input required	Service Orchestrator: LCM action, containing among others VNF packages, NSD files, infrastructure data, service policies, monitoring configurations, and service parameters.
Output produced	Infrastructure: Deployed network services, real-time monitoring data, scaling actions, lifecycle management, error reports, and resource usage statistics.
Related task(s)	T6.2

4.2.5.5 Service orchestrator

The Service orchestrator is responsible for secure and trustable deployment, placement and management of networks services and functions including slice management in cooperation with the security orchestrator. In addition to that, the service orchestration interacts with the trust domain functional blocks for static and dynamic trust assessment complemented by programable security mechanisms for security-based inputs. For a robust deployment mechanism, an internal policy verifier manages the policies and flags un-lawful anomalies. Furthermore, the service orchestrator reports back to the security orchestrator with metrics and monitoring data of the resources that are deployed and to the trust domain functional blocks with potential violations and asset listing / reference measurement for further trust evaluation and assignment.

Table 4-22 Service Orchestrator Specifications

Module name	Service orchestrator
Component description	This component shall act as the orchestrator for secure deployments (or enforcement) and maintenance(refinements) of services in the network with added security mechanisms to ensure secure placements of the network functions for: Multi-level Orchestration, Secure Placement, Network Slicing, Network Virtualization and Resource Allocation.
Responsible partners	LNVO, i2CAT
Addressed scientific locks and novelty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The service orchestrator, if relies on an input (e.g. policies derived from security monitoring results) which is prone to false positives or false negatives may lead to service failure or resource exhaustion – how do we find such anomalies from

	the service orchestrator before deployment?
Interfaces	<p>The service orchestrator in addition to its internal functionalities requires interactions with the other components or functional blocks in the iTrust6G architecture for secure deployment of services. These interactions can be stated as the following interfaces:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SA-SO: Interface between the Service Orchestrator and the Static trust assessment component. • RAE-SO: Interface between the Service Orchestrator and the Remote attestation engine. • PDP-SO: Interface between the PDP and the PEP (through the service orchestrator). • SeMo-SO: Interface between the Security Monitoring & pre-detection module and the Service Orchestrator. • ReM-SO: Interface between the Remediation Manager and the Service Orchestrator. • PrSe-SO: Interface between the Service Orchestrator and the Programmable Security Mechanism. <p>Furthermore, the internal interfaces for the Service Orchestrator are to be detailed in WP specific deliverables.</p>
Input required	<p>Remediation Manager: Remediation Actions/Strategy & Playbooks/Workflows in the form of helm charts or any other format.</p> <p>Programmable Security mechanisms: Access Request and Security Metrics, & access control request.</p> <p>Static and Dynamic Trust Assessment Component / Policy decision Point: Trust Information/ Trust Scores and access decision.</p>
Output produced	<p>Infrastructure: Secure Deployments of services.</p> <p>Infrastructure Orchestrator: Final Orchestration Configurations.</p> <p>Programmable Security Mechanism: Security configuration & access control decision.</p> <p>Security Monitoring & Pre-detection: Metrics and Monitoring data.</p> <p>Static Trust Assessment Component: List of the available devices and their services, and information about their composition.</p> <p>Policy decision Point: Access requests.</p> <p>Remediation Manager: Current network landscape.</p>
Related task(s)	T5.5, T5.1

4.3 Detailed architecture

As a conclusive step of the architecture description,

Figure 4-7 depicts a consolidated view of all the components in play in **iTrust6G** architectures in their respective layers. Additionally, the figure draws some perspectives about the purpose of each layer considering **iTrust6G**'s zero trust concept: representing the supervised *infrastructure*, contribute to a *single domain trust management*, and enacting *multi-domain collaboration* in trust and security management.

Figure 4-7: iTrust6G architecture

5 Inter-Component Flows and Processes Presentation

The previous section detailed an overview of the iTrust6G architecture, and the specification of individual functional components composing it. This included the specification of the required information and the provided capacity, and interfaces. This section provides an investigation on how these components interact to satisfy iTrust6G's intended functionality. Essentially, this section delivers a first version of the following expected technical results from *Technical Objective 1*:

- Definition of the main processes for the continuous trust assessment between services, computing resources, and users,
- Definition of the main processes for risk and threat evaluation on platform resources and mitigation,
- Definition of the main processes for the cyber-threat intelligence generation and ingestion for trust assessment.

This section also provides additional processes to illustrate how the platform is configured though policies and decisions are accounted.

To that end, for each category of processes contributing to an outcome of iTrust6G platform, this section (i) identifies individual process, and (ii) formalises them via sequence diagrams. It eventually indicates which use-case scenarios defined in iTrust6G D2.1 [1] are connected to and contribute to its implementation. Table 5-1 summarises the mapping between use-cases scenarios and identified architectural processes.

Table 5-1 Architectural Process Alignment with iTrust6G Use-Case Scenarios

Architectural Processes	Use Case 1		Use Case 2		Use Case 3			
	Sc. 1	Sc. 2	Sc. 1	Sc. 2	Sc. 1	Sc. 2	Sc. 3	Sc. 4
Application modelling, trust policy design and enactment								
Policy specification and enactment	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Explainability and collection of accountability artifacts	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
AI-driven threat intelligence for trust inference								
Threat Intelligence obtention from Cyberthreat			✓				✓	
Shared remediation enactment			✓					✓
Trust management								
Static and dynamic trust assessment			✓	✓		✓		
Service instance evaluation via remote attestation	✓	✓	✓	✓				
Forensic analysis and forensic sharing				✓				
Access request analysis decision and enforcement	✓	✓						
AI-driven security orchestration								
Threat detection and classification			✓	✓	✓		✓	
Metrics collection			✓	✓	✓		✓	
Reactive enforcement (response to threat)			✓	✓	✓	✓		
Proactive response (risk mitigation)			✓					✓

5.1 Application modelling, trust policy design and enactment

In this section, an outline of the processes involved in application modelling, trust policy design, and enactment is presented, focusing on their role within the iTrust6G platform to ensure robust policy specification, enactment, explainability, and accountability.

5.1.1 Policy specification and enactment

The goal of policy specification and enactment is to transform high-level intents, goals, or constraints

provided by stakeholders into enforceable system behaviours. These intents are collected, interpreted (Figure 4-2), and converted into policy specifications that are consumed by key components such as the Policy Decision Point (PDP), Static & Dynamic Trust Management (Figure 4-4), and the Risk Assessment Component (Figure 4-5). This process ensures that the system not only operates continuously in accordance with predefined policies but also adapts dynamically to evolving conditions and potential threats. By aligning with the specific objectives of the use cases, this component enables the system to automatically enforce operational constraints, assess trustworthiness, and manage risks in real-time. As a result, it enhances the overall safety, reliability, and adaptability of autonomous operations across all use-case scenarios, offering a flexible and responsive policy management framework that accommodates shifting environments and security challenges.

In the sequence diagram of Figure 5-1, the User submits high-level policies or intents to the Intent Processor. The Intent Processor translates these abstract intents into actionable system behaviours and forwards the translated policies to the Policy Decision Point (PDP) for validation. Once the PDP validates the policies, the Intent Processor coordinates with the Static & Dynamic Trust Assessment to verify trust and access control policies. Simultaneously, the Intent Processor sends security policies to Security Orchestration (SO), which implements the appropriate security measures. Explainability and collection of accountability artifacts.

5.1.2 Explainability and collection of accountability artifacts

The Explainability component ensures that decisions made by AI algorithms, such as those in the security threat detection and classification component (Figure 4-5), are transparent and understandable to human operators. This includes explaining how the AI system identifies potential security threats, classifies them, and informs system actions. Additionally, access request logs from the Policy Decision Point (PDP), as well as identity attributes provided by the Identity Provider (IdP), are captured in the accounting ledger for traceability. This process makes the decision-making process explainable to the user by providing clear insights into how the system's AI models interact with security policies and identity attributes to determine access or deny actions. The accounting ledger acts as a repository of all these decision points, allowing for comprehensive auditing and accountability.

Figure 5-2 shows the sequence diagram representing the policy specification and enactment process. All relevant information is sent to the Accounting Ledger, including identity attributes, access request logs, threat detection decisions, or risk assessments. Once the Accounting Ledger has collected and recorded this data, it is forwarded to the Explainability component. Explainability then analyses the complete dataset and based on this analysis, provides the user with clear and comprehensible explanations of how the system's decisions were made. This process ensures that the decision-making is transparent and understandable. By coordinating the flow of information in this manner, a clear and auditable understanding of the security system's actions and decisions is achieved.

Figure 5-1: Sequence diagram representing the policy specification and enactment process

Figure 5-2: Sequence diagram representing the policy specification and enactment process

5.2 AI-driven threat intelligence for trust inference

This section details the process of obtaining cyber threat information related to a detected and classified threat, and how this information is consumed from the same or different domains to determine their remediation strategy.

5.2.1 Threat Intelligence obtention from Cyberthreat

The Threat Intelligence obtention from Cyberthreat process serves the cyber-threat intelligence generation that exploits monitoring and detection capabilities to elicit sharable knowledge about detected threats in one tenant (administrative domain), to enable proactive remediation in other tenants (*Result R3.2*). The process implements part of *UC2 - Scenario 1*, and *UC3 - Scenario 3* where the focus is on validating the operational security mechanisms of the iTrust6G platform to ensure that it can detect and mitigate attacks, thereby maintaining trust and compliance with security policies.

Figure 5-3 shows the sequence diagram representing process threat intelligence acquired from cyberthreat. In this sequence, an identified threat triggers a set of actions:

1. Security Threat Detection and Classification component detects a threat using information provided by the External Threat DB and the CTI Platform Components.
2. Information regarding the specific classified threat is being pushed back to CTI platform along with any additionally generated knowledge based on the existing and newly added information.
3. Static Trust Assessment component receives threat related information from the External Threat DB and the CTI platform to provide the trust inference. Based on the result, the CTI platform receives this information to update, if applicable, its content.
4. The generated CTI becomes available for the entire platform and especially for the components Risk Assessment, Security Monitoring & pre-detection, and Static Trust Assessment.

5.2.2 Shared remediation enactment

One aspect of the collaboration between tenant/administrative domain in iTrust6G is the ability to exchange remediation strategy to enable collaborative assessment against identified cyber-threat. The objective of this process is to enact an evaluation of the security posture of a domain given occurrence of a cyber-threat or newly found vulnerability and obtain the enactment of a mitigation strategy through playbook (*Result R3.3 Remediation playbook for Cyber Threat Intelligence*).

Figure 5-3: Sequence diagram representing process threat intelligence acquired from cyberthreat

Figure 5-4: Sequence diagram representing the shared remediation enactment process

This process is contributing directly to the implementation of the *first scenario of the second use-case* and the *fourth scenarios of the third use-case*. Figure 5-4 shows the sequence diagram of the shared remediation enactment process. This process is launched when another collaborating domain notified the CTI platform that has detected and classified a threat in its infrastructure. Here the hypothesis is that an adequate abstract remediation has been shared in the remediation playbook repository and is available to the tenant. Upon this, the CTI platform triggers a notification to inform the Remediation Manager of the situation from another domain. The remediation manager then gather intelligence from the Service Orchestrator, the CTI platform and the playbook repository to evaluate which mitigation strategies are to be used and submit them to the risk assessment component. Based on its feedback, the remediation manager evaluates if mitigation is needed in the domain or not.

5.3 Trust management

This section describes an outline of the processes involved in trust evaluation, including both static and dynamic analysis, as well as trust evaluation using AI techniques. This section also examines the mechanisms and their interactions with service authentication, management, service control, and forensic analysis. Additionally, this section provides schemas illustrating how these components operate and interact within the iTrust6G project.

5.3.1 Static and dynamic trust assessment

The continuous scrutinisation of the resources is one of the founding pillars for ZT paradigm. In this subsection, we detail iTrust6G process to continuously conduct trust assessment on the resources in interaction with the resource of the domain (e.g. *network functions*). This process lies the foundation of the trust management system and trust evaluation algorithms that are used in access request evaluation and are expected outcomes of the *Technical Objective 4*. This process implements part of *UC2 - Scenario 1, 2 and UC3 - Scenario 2*.

Figure 5-5: Sequence diagram representing the static and dynamic trust assessment process

This process is continuously run during the lifespan of the platform. We It is first assumed that the trust inference component is providing the necessary information for trust evaluation from the security orchestration context. This includes the Threat Intelligence obtained from the forensic analysis.

The first part of the process regards the evaluation of the compliance of assets based on static properties. To that end, the list of know vulnerabilities and the list of available assets are retrieved respectively from the external threat database and the service orchestrator. A static evaluation is conducted, provides a signal for trust score calculation on the AI trust evaluator.

Meanwhile, the AI trust evaluator gather inputs also provided from the remote attestation engine, the security monitoring & pre-detection, and conducts continuously trust score evaluation. Those trust scores are sent to the Remediation Manager to impact the selection of remediation strategy while recommendations for optimised security strategy are sent to the accounting ledger & explainability and the evaluated trust information. Afterward the score is sent to the evidence repository and accounting ledger, to inform access control decisions.

5.3.2 Service instance evaluation via remote attestation

Attesting the state of an entity involves verifying it through a remote verifier, ensuring the entity's integrity and trustworthiness. This process plays a role in assessing trust links in all *use case 1 and use case 2*. By providing detailed information about the nodes' integrity, it strengthens the overall trust framework within these scenarios.

Figure 5-6 shows sequence of the process service evaluation via remote attestation. First, the service orchestrator must register the entities with the RA engine by providing node information and reference values. The RA engine can then send periodic attestation requests to all registered entities. Upon receiving these requests, the nodes' attestors collect their integrity values and return them to the RA engine, ensuring the integrity of the data. Finally, the RA engine compares the collected values with the reference values and sends the attestation results to the AI trust evaluator, which uses this information with others to generate a trust score for each entity.

5.3.3 Forensic analysis and forensic sharing

To acquire a complete image of the effects of a cybersecurity incident, forensic analytics techniques must be applied to all information available from the system, from images to logs, alerts and any other available. This process plays a role in *UC2 -Scenario 2* and specifically in increasing the robustness of the operation security of the project.

Figure 5-6: Sequence diagram representing process service evaluation via remote attestation

Figure 5-7: Sequence diagram representing the forensic analysis and forensic sharing process

Figure 5-7 illustrates the sequence diagram of the forensic analysis and forensic sharing process. First the CTI Platform is informed of the presence of a cybersecurity incident by any of the other modules, either during the incident or afterwards it forwards any information including original datasets to the Forensic Analyser. The remote Attestation engine follows the same logic. The forensic analyser uses this data to construct the report about the nature of the incident and forwards it back to the CTI platform and Threat detection and classification module.

5.3.4 Access request analysis decision and enforcement

The Access request analysis, decision, and enforcement process aims to manage and control access to resources within the system, by systematically evaluating and acting upon access requests. It aligns with *use cases UC1 - Scenario 1 & 2*, where the focus is on ensuring that only authorized users can access specific resources while maintaining a clear and auditable decision-making process. This process ensures that access requests are thoroughly analysed, decisions are made based on established policies, and enforcement actions are executed effectively.

Figure 5-8 represents the sequence diagram for the access request analysis decision and enforcement process. The process begins when an access request is emitted from the infrastructure, as depicted in the sequence diagram. This request is received by the PEP, which is responsible for handling access requests and ensuring compliance with security policies. The PEP forwards the request to the Policy PDP for evaluation. The PDP assesses the request against the defined policies and decides regarding access. Once the PDP has rendered its decision, the result is sent back to the PEP. Depending on the decision, the PEP enforces the access policy by granting or denying access to the resource or takes appropriate action based on the decision. This interaction sequence ensures that access requests are processed systematically, decisions are made according to established policies, and enforcement is accurately executed on the infrastructure.

Figure 5-8: Sequence diagram representing the access request analysis decision and enforcement process

5.4 AI-driven security orchestration

In this section, details of the process of related AI-driven security orchestration, serving threat and risk management in iTrust6G platform.

5.4.1 Threat detection and classification

The Threat Detection and Classification process plays a crucial role in assessing and responding to potential threats by inferring trust intelligence and classifying detected threats. It outlines how AI-integrated components leverage security metrics to identify, analyse, and mitigate malicious activities. This process is integral to implementing *scenarios 1 and 2 of the second use case*, where proactive detection and mitigation measures safeguard against threats, and *scenario 2* focuses on identifying compromised entities. Additionally, it addresses *scenario 1 of the third use case* by evaluating the effectiveness of detection and mitigation mechanisms against persistent attacks and *scenario 3* by illustrating the classification process.

Figure 5-9 is the sequence diagram representing the threat detection and classification process. In this sequence, the process of how security metrics inform AI-integrated components to derive trust intelligence and determine countermeasures is explained:

Upon detection of a threat from the Security Monitoring and Pre-Detection component, relevant security and detection metrics are forwarded to the Security Threat Detection & Classification component, where advanced AI/ML models are used for thorough analysis and decision-making. Threat insights are shared with the Federated Learning Models component for collaborative model updates, allowing different domains to improve their detection algorithms without sharing raw data. Concurrently, the Security Threat Detection & Classification component communicates threat specifications to Trust Inference. Threat insights guide the Remediation Manager component in determining and enforcing appropriate countermeasures, such as configuring security policies and deploying additional controls, to mitigate identified threats effectively.

5.4.2 Metrics collection

The metric collection process serves the retrieval of metrics from operated network resources to serve the evaluation of security posture of a domain. This process is ancillary toward CTI generation (technical objective 2), risk/vulnerability and attack handling (*technical objective 4*). This process contributes to the implementation of the *two scenarios of the second use case* by tooling the detection of the variation of the baseline and enact the continuous security monitoring. It also serves the implementation of the *scenarios 1 and 3 of the third use cases* via the enabling of security metrics collection, their collection by a SIEM and usage by threat detection models. Figure 5-10 details the expected interactions between components.

Figure 5-9: Sequence diagram representing the threat detection and classification process

Figure 5-10: Sequence diagram representing the metrics collection process

In this process, we consider the case of a network service operated in an administrative domain, and interaction with data plane resources and services located in foreign domain. The network services may continuously be streaming specific security metrics if programmed with specialised security mechanisms to iTrust6G service orchestrator. In every case, the operation of the network service generates operation metrics from its instances. Those metrics and monitoring data (possibly including collected security metrics) are reported to the security monitoring and pre-detection for pre-processing. In case the data reveals suspicious activity, (i) potential security events, are sent to the trust inference components for ulterior correlation if a threat is detected and (ii) the detection metrics are transferred to the security threat detection and classification components for analysis and decision-making.

5.4.3 Reactive enforcement (response to threat)

The Reactive Enforcement process activates when a threat is detected, either by an external administrator or through an automated detection module, such as the risk detection or classification component. The goal is to immediately respond to ongoing security incidents by deploying appropriate assets to neutralize the detected threat. This process supports the system's ability to react in real-time, aligning with the objectives of maintaining service continuity and securing network resources against active threats.

This process implements part of the third use case, scenario 1, where detected threats trigger remediation actions that aim to maintain network security without disrupting operational services.

Figure 5-11: Sequence diagram representing the reactive enforcement process

The process also aligns with technical objectives that focus on risk handling and immediate threat response. Figure 5-11 illustrates the sequence diagram representing the reactive enforcement process. In this sequence, an identified threat triggers a set of actions:

1. Threat Detection Module (e.g., Security Threat Detection and Classification component) detects a threat and signals the Remediation Manager.
2. The Remediation Manager initiates the evidence collection process from the Service Orchestrator, the CTI platform and the remediation playbook repository to elicit a subset of viable remediation strategies.
3. Risk Assessment Component is contacted to evaluate the remediation propositions and issue a risk profile evaluating their expected efficacy.
4. The Remediation Manager selects the most adequate mitigation strategy (e.g., security patch, service configuration), and enacts its deployment: It determines if any additional security mechanisms should optionally be deployed, or if existing instances should undergo some lifecycle management action and evaluate needs for re-configuration.
5. The Remediation Manager interfaces with the Service Orchestrator to deploy supporting programmable enablers in the infrastructure to neutralize the ongoing threat.
6. The enacted playbook used for remediation is saved into the remediation playbook repository, to be reused and shared if needed.

This ensures that the system can maintain operational integrity, quickly react to new threats, and restore trust within the system after mitigation actions are taken.

5.4.4 Proactive response (risk mitigation)

The Proactive Response process focuses on mitigating potential risks before they become active threats for the administrative domain. This is initiated either by an external risk assessment entity or the system's own risk detection module. The objective is to enhance the security posture by deploying protective assets pre-emptively, reducing the likelihood of security breaches or vulnerabilities being exploited. This process aligns with proactive risk handling strategies aimed at preventing service disruption and maintaining operational integrity.

This process implements part of the second use case scenario, where pre-emptive measures are taken to address vulnerabilities or potential risks identified during ongoing operations. The process contributes to the technical objective of continuous risk evaluation and mitigation.

Figure 5-12 shows the sequence diagram representing proactive response process. In this sequence, a risk is detected, and actions are initiated to prevent future threats:

1. The CTI platform communicates to the remediation manager the occurrence of a cyberthreat in another domain that might requires to be addressed.
2. The remediation manager initiates the evidence collection process from the service orchestrator, the CTI platform and the remediation playbook repository to elicit a subset of viable mitigation strategies.
3. Risk Assessment Component is contacted to evaluate the mitigation propositions and issue a risk profile evaluating their expected efficacy.
4. Based on this information, the remediation manager confirms or denies the need for enacting mitigation measures.

Figure 5-12: Sequence diagram representing proactive response process

5. If this is the case:
 - a. The Remediation Manager selects the most adequate mitigation strategy (e.g., security patch, service configuration), and enacts its deployment: It determines if any additional security mechanisms should optionally be deployed, or if existing instances should undergo some lifecycle management action and evaluate needs for re-configuration.
 - b. The Remediation Manager interfaces with the Service Orchestrator to deploy supporting programmable enablers in the infrastructure to neutralize the ongoing threat.
 - c. The enacted playbook used for remediation is saved into the remediation playbook repository, to be reused and shared if needed.

This proactive response process ensures that the system is continuously reinforced against potential security vulnerabilities, helping maintain a high level of trust and security in dynamic and evolving network environments.

6 Summary and Conclusions

iTrust6G D2.2 contains the initial version of iTrust6G architecture, and a description of the ZT concept serving as foundation. iTrust6G has grounded the work on the several pivotal domains, namely collaborative threat intelligence, trust models and evaluation, and security management. The main achievements reported in this document are:

- Analysis of the state-of-the-art, and identification of relevant standardisation bodies;
- Proposition of a ZT concept for delivering end-to-end trust connectivity for 6G networks;
- Description of a system architecture for trust and security in a multi-tenant 6G telecom platform;
- Definition of the main processes for the continuous trust assessment between services, computing resources, and users;
- Definition of the main processes for risk and threat evaluation on platform resources and mitigation;
- Definition of the main processes for the cyber-threat intelligence generation and ingestion for trust assessment.

Following the delivery of the initial architecture and main founding processes, iTrust6G D2.2 provides a framework for the investigation, design and implementations in the iTrust6G WP3, WP4 and WP5, and will lay the initial foundation for the integration activity in WP 6. The content of this document will continue to evolve based on the outcomes of the project's further activities during the first period of the project and will be iterated as the final version of the architecture in the upcoming iTrust6G D2.4.

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